

EVALUATION OF VERMICOMPOST AND *RHIZOBIUM* INOCULATION ON
NODULATION, YIELD, AND YIELD TRAITS OF COMMON BEAN (*PHASEOLUS
VULGARIS* L.) VARIETIES AND SELECTED SOIL PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES
AT MESKAN DISTRICT, GURAGE ZONE, SOUTHERN ETHIOPIA

M.Sc. THESIS

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HAWASSA UNIVERSITY, HAWASSA, ETHIOPIA

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ADVISORS' APPROVAL SHEET
SCHOOL OF GRADUATE STUDIES
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This is to certify that the thesis entitled “Evaluation of Vermicompost and Rhizobium Inoculation on Nodulation, Yield, and Yield Traits of Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Varieties and Selected Soil Physico-Chemical Properties at Meskan District, Gurage Zone, Southern Ethiopia,” submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master with specialization in Soil science under the graduate program of the Department of Plant and Horticultural Sciences, and has been carried out by Bikiltu Tolessa under our supervision. Therefore, we recommend that the student has fulfilled the requirements and hence hereby can submit the thesis to the department.

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this thesis to my beloved Father Mr. Tolessa Sedi and my family for their concern, prayer, patience, encouragement, and love in the success of my life.

STATEMENT OF AUTHOR

I declare that this thesis is my bona fide work and all sources of materials used for this thesis have been duly acknowledged. I solemnly declare that this thesis is not submitted to any other institution anywhere for the award of any academic degree, diploma, or certificate.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AGB	Above-Ground Biomass
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
Bd	Bulk Density
BNF	Biological Nitrogen Fixation
BOF	Bureau of Agriculture
CEC	Cation Exchange Capacity
CSA	Central Statistical Agency
CV	Coefficient of variation
ECe	Electro-conductivity
EIAR	Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research
Ethio-SIS	Ethiopian Soil Information System
FYM	Farmyard Manure
Ha	Hectare
HI	Harvest Index
m.a.s.l	Meters Above Sea Level
MoARD	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
TN	Total Nitrogen

OC	Organic Carbon
OM	Organic Matter
Ppm	Parts Per Million
R	Rhizobium
SAS	Statistical Analysis Software
SNF	Symbiotic Nitrogen Fixation
SNNPR	Southern Nations, Nationalities, and People's Region
LSD	Least Significant Difference
VAR	Variety
VC	Vermicompost

Evaluation of Responses to Vermicompost and *Rhizobium* Inoculation on Nodulation, Yield, and Yield Traits of Common Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Varieties and Selected Soil Physico-Chemical Properties at Meskan, Gurage zone, Southern Ethiopia.

Bikiltu Tolessa, Supervisors: Shimelis Gezachew (PhD), Wasie Haile (PhD)

ABSTRACT

*Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is an important grain legume in Ethiopia. However, the national average yield is very low compared to its potential yield mainly because of low soil fertility. The study was conducted at Meskan district of Gurage Zone to evaluate the effects of vermicompost and *Rhizobium* inoculation on nodulation, yield, and yield traits of common bean varieties and selected soil physico-chemical properties during the 2022 main cropping season. A factorial combination of three Vermicompost (VC) rates (0, 4, 8 t ha⁻¹), two common bean varieties (SER-125 and Hawassa Dume), and *Rhizobium* inoculation (Inoculated and Uninoculated) were laid out in RCB design in factorial arrangement with three replications. Representative soil samples from each plot were taken after harvest from the depths of 0-30cm and were analyzed for VC effects on soil physico-chemical properties. The N difference method was used to quantify biological nitrogen fixation. Growth and yield parameters were taken. The data were analyzed using SAS software Version 9.4. Results revealed that VC application had significantly ($p < 0.01$) increased ECe from 0.54 to 0.72 ds/m, CEC from 21.83 to 26.08 (cmol(+)/kg), organic carbon from 1.15 to 1.46%, Total Nitrogen (TN) from 0.099 to 0.13% and the interaction of Vermicompost and *Rhizobium* had significantly ($P < 0.01$) increased av.P from 6.70 to 13.95 mg/kg. VC increased Soil moisture content (SMC) at 30 days after planting from 28.57 to 37.36%, at 60 days from 26.54 to 32.62%, and from 17 to 19.92% at 90 days after planting. VC X *Rhizobium* X variety significantly influenced days to 50% flowering, effective number of nodules, pods per plant, seed per pod. N-fixed and % Ndfa of common bean significantly increased at 4 t/ha VC, *Rhizobium* inoculated application on Hawassa Dume variety. Highest grain yield 3641.65 kg/ha ($P < 0.01$) was achieved with 8 t/ha VC applied on Hawassa Dume variety. Integrated application of 8 t/ha VC and *Rhizobium* inoculation on Hawassa Dume variety offers a promising strategy for enhancing common bean yields. Further research across seasons is recommended to solidify these findings and provide wider applicability. In essence, this experiment provides Ethiopian farmers with a sustainable and effective tool to increase their common bean yields, leading to improved food security and economic prosperity.*

KEYWORDS: Soil fertility, Nitrogen fixation, Soil properties, Yield components, Yield

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and Justification

In many lowlands and mid-altitude regions of Ethiopia, smallholder farmers view common bean as their primary cash crop and source of cheap protein. The crop is usually grown by subsistence farmers as sole crop and/or inter cropped with either cereals or tree crops (CSA, 2000).

Common beans are used in traditional cuisines in Ethiopia. More of the crop is grown for domestic use than for export. The most common way to prepare dry beans is as "nifro" (cooked whole grains), which is typically combined with sorghum or maize, "wat" (local soup), and also "kocho". Fresh beans are well-liked for their flavor and capacity to crack (mature, whole non-dried grain) (MoARD, 2016). Dry seeds are well known for being a cheap and accessible source of protein while lacking sulfur amino acids (Erbersdobler, H.F *et al.* 2017).

Additionally, common bean seeds are a good source of vitamins, minerals, dietary fiber, starch, and complex carbohydrate. Common bean seeds, like other legumes, contain a variety of bioactive substances, such as lectins, phytates, oligosaccharides, and phenolic compounds, which have metabolic roles in both humans and animals (Angela *et al.*, 2010).

The country's central, eastern, and southern regions are where the majority of common beans are produced, although the crop has been grown in other areas as well (CSA, 2000).

The majority of common bean cultivation in Ethiopia is concentrated in the Oromia (43%), Amhara (25%), and Southern Nations Nationalities and Peoples regions (29%) (Berhanu *et al.*, 2018). Farmers are drawn to this crop because it matures quickly, allowing them to generate additional income by selling surplus beans from double cropping in a year (Berhanu *et al.*, 2018).

In 2014, the land area dedicated to common bean production in Ethiopia was 323,318 hectares, which decreased to 311,583 hectares by 2020 (CSA, 2021). Despite the 4% reduction in land coverage, the total crop production increased from 51,373 tons to 55,256 tons (CSA, 2021). This increase can be attributed to the improved productivity level of common bean grain yield, which reached 1.8 tons per hectare, surpassing the actual land area harvested (CSA, 2021). However, the grain yield achieved by farmers in their fields is significantly lower than the yield recorded at research stations (~3.0 tons per hectare) (MoANR, 2016).

This indicates a yield gap of approximately 1.2 tons per hectare between farmers and the potential yield of 3.5 tons per hectare reported in Ethiopia (Amare & Kassahun, 2021; Berhanu *et al.*, 2018; Mohammed & Feleke, 2022). This Gap might be because of depleted soil nutrient levels, particularly phosphorus and nitrogen, limit bean productivity Yigezu *et al.* (2022).

Farmers often lack access to improved cultivars with higher yields, disease resistance, and adaptation to specific environments (Yigezu *et al.*, 2022; Njoroge *et al.*, 2013). Limited access to affordable, high-quality seeds of improved varieties restricts adoption and yield improvement (Njoroge *et al.*, 2013; Araya *et al.*, 2010). Limited knowledge about improved production practices, including intercropping, crop rotation, and soil conservation, hampers yield potential (Holden *et al.*, 2009; Wortmann *et al.*, 2012).

Farmers often struggle to afford fertilizers, pesticides, and other essential inputs due to financial constraints or limited availability (Yigezu *et al.*, 2022; Wortmann *et al.*, 2012). To address these constraints and improve common bean production, further research is needed, utilizing advanced technologies and innovative approaches in the crop production chain (Berhanu *et al.*, 2018). By implementing these strategies, it is possible to bridge the significant 34% grain yield gap between farmers' current yields and the potential yield (Berhanu *et al.*, 2018).

In low-input agriculture, bio-fertilizers and organic fertilizers are inexpensive and environmentally safe sources of plant nutrients for sustaining crop output. Vermicompost, which is an organic fertilizer, plays a beneficial role in providing organic nutrition and promoting plant growth (Simsek, 2011). The use of vermicompost is considered a sustainable practice that can enhance plant growth and increase yields (Castillo *et al.*, 2010).

Research has demonstrated that the application of vermicompost, either alone or in combination with other organic fertilizers, has proven effective in improving the growth and yield of various crops, including common bean, faba bean and soybean (Javed, 2013).

Similarly, applying organic manures has a good impact on the physical and biochemical characteristics of the soil. It reduces soil bulk density, raises CEC, builds up beneficial soil microorganisms, improves sound soil structure, and strengthens stable soil aggregates. It also improves soil water holding capacity (Doran, 1995; Drinkwater *et al.*, 1995; Stamatiadis *et al.*, 1999).

Recently, the importance of bio-fertilizers in sustainable crop production has come to light, either on their own or in combination with organic or inorganic fertilizers (Kennedy *et al.*, 2004; Bloemberg *et al.*, 2000; Abdullahi and Sheriff, 2013). Rhizobium seed inoculation has been shown to improve nodulation, nitrogen uptake, growth, and yield characteristics in legume crops (Sogut, 2006). When Rhizobium inoculation is combined with a high N-containing fertilizer, however, the efficiency of inoculation on nodulation and N derived from the atmosphere via biological N fixing is diminished (Ogutcu *et al.*, 2008). Clayton *et al.* (2004), for example, studied the response of field peas to nitrogen fertilizer and found that more than 40 kg N ha⁻¹ reduced nodulation and N fixation.

These bacteria have key roles in the production of hormones that stimulate plant development, the cycling of nutrients, which improves the availability and uptake of nutrients by plants, nitrogen fixation, plant health improvement, drought resistance, and soil reclamation (Barea *et al.*, 1998; Dobbelaere *et al.*, 2001; Hodge *et al.*, 2001; Bonfante, 2003; Vasseyy, 2003). The integrated application of high-quality organic fertilizer (vermicompost) and Rhizobium inoculation is needed to boost faba bean production in low fertile soils. Adjusting organic input increased peanut production and nodulation (Agegnehu *et al.*, 2015).

1.2. Statement of the Problem

In recent times, chemical fertilizers have been pivotal in meeting crop nutrient requirements, promoting crop growth. However, their application in fields can have adverse environmental impacts, contributing to environmental degradation, soil fertility loss, reduced agricultural productivity, and soil degradation. Moreover, chemical fertilizers are costlier compared to organic fertilizers, exacerbating economic burdens. To address these issues, organic fertilizers like vermicompost emerge as superior alternatives. Presently, the utilization of organic manures and biofertilizers, including vermicompost, has reduced reliance on chemical fertilizers, providing high-quality products devoid of harmful agro-chemicals, thus ensuring human safety. Furthermore, vermicompost application may mitigate environmental pollution associated with the industrial production of chemical fertilizers (Malik *et al.*, 2009). However, various constraints impact the yield and overall stability of common bean production. In the study area, there is a lack of comprehensive research on the effects of vermicompost and *Rhizobium* inoculation on nodulation, yield, and yield traits of common bean varieties, as well as their influence on selected soil physico-chemical properties.

Consequently, the specific problem lies in the limited understanding of the potential benefits and interactions associated with the application of vermicompost and Rhizobium inoculation in common bean production in the targeted area. This knowledge gap hampers the adoption of sustainable practices that could enhance nodulation, yield, and yield traits of common bean varieties while also improving soil health.

Therefore, the objective of this research is to evaluate the effects of vermicompost and Rhizobium inoculation on nodulation, yield, and yield traits of common bean varieties, and to evaluate their impact on selected soil physico-chemical properties. By addressing this problem, the study aims to contribute to the development of sustainable agricultural practices that can enhance common bean production and improve soil fertility in the region (Tiwari, 2002). However, currently, there is limited documented information regarding the response of common beans to inoculation and vermicompost application in the area, necessitating extensive research and evaluation (IFPRI, 2010b).

1.3. OBJECTIVES

1.3.1. General Objective

- To evaluate the effects of vermicompost and *rhizobium* inoculation on nodulation, yield, and yield traits of common bean varieties and selected soil physical-chemical properties at Meskan district, Gurage zone, southern Ethiopia.

1.3.2. Specific Objectives

- To determine vermicompost effects on selected soil properties (soil moisture content, bulk density, OC, CEC, pH).
- To estimate biological nitrogen fixation and determine the effect of *Rhizobium*, vermicompost application and varieties on the estimate of nitrogen fixation..
- To determine the effect on common bean variety on growth and productivity of the crop

1.4. Research Questions

- What are the effects of vermicompost on selected soil properties (soil moisture content, bulk density, OC, CEC, pH)?
- What are the effects of *Rhizobium*, vermicompost application and varieties on the estimate of nitrogen fixation?
- Does common bean variety affect growth and productivity of the crop?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Origin and Distribution of Common Bean

The common bean underwent domestication in two distinct regions: the Mesoamerican gene pool, spanning from northern Mexico to Colombia, and the Andean gene pool, extending from southern Peru to Northwestern Argentina (Koenig and Gepts, 1989; Koinange and Gepts, 1992; Freyre *et al.*, 1996). Initially domesticated in Central America, evidence suggests multiple domestications occurred in Tropical America, including regions like Mexico, Guatemala, and Peru (Kay, 1979). Presently, the common bean is cultivated on all continents except Antarctica (Singh, 1999), likely introduced to Ethiopia by the Portuguese in the sixteenth century (Wortman, 1998).

Following domestication, the common bean spread globally, with cultivars from Mesoamerica and the Andes reaching lowland South America and Africa (Gepts and Debouck, 1991). Mesoamerican cultivars dominated in the southwest, while Andean cultivars prevailed in Africa, Europe, and the northeast (Gepts and Debouck, 1991).

Domestication altered the common bean's form, morphology, and phenology, notably affecting growth pattern, seed size, retention, and maturity. Domestication favored smaller, denser plants with short internodes, reduced climbing ability, fewer, thicker stems, and larger leaves (Debouck, 1991).

Selection processes led to determinate and indeterminate common bean cultivars with compact growth habits. Notably, variations in pod and seed sizes distinguish domesticated common beans from their wild ancestors. Cultivated common beans exhibit considerable variability in seed size and edible components, including green, immature pods and dry seeds (Debouck, 1991).

Common bean plants display polymorphism, assuming various forms, including climbing, erect, and bushy (up to 60 cm tall) with stems reaching up to three meters. Their compound leaves feature three oval leaflets with smooth edges and pointed tips. The plants produce clusters of tiny, variegated blooms, typically white, pink, or purplish, measuring about 1 cm long. Pod development occurs over two to three weeks, resulting in pods of varying colors—green, yellow, black, or purple—often flat or cylinder-shaped and containing two to four seeds.

2.2. Common bean production in Ethiopia

In recent times, the common bean, also referred to as haricot bean or navy bean, has gained significant importance in Ethiopia owing to its dual role in domestic consumption and export trade. Dry beans are marketed both as fresh immature beans and dry flour beans in Ethiopian food markets. The majority of production is attributed to smallholder farmers, particularly in the central Rift valley, followed by regions like southern, eastern, and western Ethiopia (Tsedeke, 1995). However, production has extended to other regions, including Afar, Amhara, Tigray, Somali, Gambella, and Benshangul Gumuz (Dawit, 2005).

While the specific types of common beans cultivated in these regions and their contributions to domestic and export markets remain partially documented, it's noteworthy that Oromia and the Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples Region (SNNPR) collectively account for approximately 85 percent of the national production, averaging between 100,000 and 200,000 metric tons per year (Ferris and Kaganzi, 2008).

Various factors such as soil type, altitude, and agro-ecological conditions influence common bean production in Ethiopia. Smallholder farmers typically cultivate it on fragmented plots for household consumption and sale. White beans serve as the primary export commodity, while red beans and other varieties are mainly consumed domestically. Among commercial varieties, pure red and pure white beans have gained prominence due to rising market demand. Farmers in the central rift valley exhibit clear preferences for common bean varieties based on market value, consumption preferences, early maturation, and overall field performance (Endeshaw *et al.*, 2011).

2.3. The Role and Importance of Vermicompost

Compost prepared by using earthworms through the process called vermicomposting is called vermicompost (Garg *et al.*, 2006). Vermicomposting is a straightforward biotechnological method of composting in which specific species of earthworms are employed to speed up the waste-to-product conversion process and provide a superior final product (Garg *et al.*, 2006; Nagavallema *et al.* 2006). Processing the material as rapidly and effectively as feasible is the aim. Composting and worm composting are different processes (Garg *et al.*, 2006).

It is a mesospheric technique that uses earthworms and microorganisms that are active between 10 and 32 degrees Celsius (not ambient temperature but temperature within the pile of moist organic material).

Due to usage of chemical fertilizers and inappropriate irrigation in recent years, some agricultural lands are subjected to soil salinity, destroying agroecosystems and making production unsustainable (Proceeding of a First National Workshop on Organic Farming, 2006). Because of the negative effects of continued usage of chemical fertilizers and pesticides, organic manures like vermicompost are all the more important. (Shahid, S.A.; Al-Shankiti, Res. 2013). In contrast to NPK fertilizers, vermicompost provides a wide variety of important macro and micronutrients for healthy plant growth (Surindra, 2009).

Vermicompost is now a crucial component of an organic agricultural system, according to report from the First National Workshop on Organic Farming (2006). It is one of the bio-fertilizers that helps boost soil porosity and water-holding capacity while also promoting plant growth. It contains all necessary plant nutrients, vitamins, enzymes, growth hormones, and advantageous microorganisms. It also serves as a soil activator, soil conditioner, and soil fertility enhancer (Garg *et al.*, 2006). Any organic material, including green plants, animal dung, poultry manure, sheep manure, leaves, and ash, can be used to prepare it Suparno *et al.*(2013). Stated that the basic components are layered in the order a layer of crop residues/green plants (20 cm)= 60%, layer of top soil/ash (2-4 cm)= 10% and layer of manure (5-10 cm)= 30%, and the decomposition process is facilitated by earthworms. The fresh organic matter incorporated in the compost bin and above 75% moisture should be maintained for free motility and breathing of the worms.

2.4. Soil responses to vermicompost applications

Vermicompost applications enhance soil fertility by enriching it with micro and macro nutrients, vitamins, enzymes, and hormones, thereby promoting plant development through the regulation of physico-chemical properties (Makulec, 2002; Sinha *et al.*, 2009; Hazra, 2016). Vermicompost products contain nutrients in a form readily accessible to plants, attributed to the mesophilic composting process following thermophilic composting (Pathma and Sakthivel, 2012; Lim *et al.*, 2012). The resulting material, rich in humic acids, from vermicompost contributes to increased plant biomass and root development (Erdal *et al.*, 2000; Sönmez *et al.*, 2013; Delibacak and Ogun, 2016).

Moreover, vermicompost aids in nutrient retention within the soil by regulating soil pH and increasing electrical conductivity without inducing salinity issues (Argüello *et al.*, 2006). It enhances the soil's water-air balance and increases macro porosity from 50 to 500 microns, thus improving nutrient retention (Marinari *et al.*, 2000). The increased surface area of vermicompost augments micro-porosity, facilitating nutrient retention (Shi-wei and Fu-zhen, 1991; Ali *et al.*, 2015). Compared to thermophilic compost and inorganic fertilizers, vermicompost has a more positive impact on plant growth and soil structure, particularly in degraded tropical soils (Jouquet *et al.*, 2011).

Vermicompost products possess antibiotic properties due to their biochemical hormones, which can enhance soil structure and increase the concentration of plant growth hormones (Edwards and Bohlen, 1996; Edwards and Aracon, 2004; Singh *et al.*, 2008). Additionally, vermicompost has been found to reduce the concentration of heavy metals in soil, offering a solution to environmental concerns related to heavy metal accumulation (Dominguez, 2004). Earthworms

present in vermicompost can accumulate heavy metals, thus reducing their presence in soil (Tacırođlu *et al.*, 2016).

Furthermore, vermicompost, rich in organic matter, enhances soil fertility by stimulating microbial biomass concentration and phosphatase enzyme activity (Şahin *et al.*, 2016). Vermicomposting is recognized as an efficient method for environmentally and economically sustainable waste management, especially given the increasing global volume of organic waste (Singh and Singh, 2017), estimated to reach 2.2 billion tons annually by 2025.

2.5. Plant Responses to Vermicompost

The presence of organic matter in crop production has consistently been linked to increased yields as it can be decomposed by an active microbial population, releasing nutrients (Gopal *et al.*, 2009; Goyal *et al.*, 2005; Kumar-Srivastava *et al.*, 2007; Lazcano *et al.*, 2008). Vermicompost, in particular, offers advantages over traditional thermophilic compost by enhancing microbial populations and altering the physical and chemical properties of composted organic material (Sampedro & Whalen, 2007).

However, excessive use of vermicompost can lead to poor germination, slow development rates, and reduced yields likely due to elevated electrical conductivity from excessive salt concentrations. Optimal substitution rates of vermicompost in growth media are typically below 50%, with rates as low as 10% still providing benefits, which can contribute to its economic viability (Atiyeh *et al.*, 2000; Atiyeh *et al.*, 2002; Subler *et al.*, 1998).

Vermicomposts have demonstrated potential in inhibiting soil-borne plant diseases, although results vary based on factors such as feedstock, pathosystem, and temperature (Szech and Smolinska, 2001; Szech *et al.*, 1993; Scheuerell *et al.*, 2005; Ascitutto *et al.*, 2006). The digestion of organic materials by earthworms alters soil microbial populations, impacting agroecosystems and overall plant health. Vermicompost, with its high population of disease-suppressing microorganisms, promotes competition among viable plant pathogens across a broader soil area, potentially hastening crop maturation and reducing disease spread (Enami *et al.*, 2001).

Additionally, vermicompost is believed to reduce populations of arthropod pests and associated damage by containing higher levels of phenols, which are water-soluble and unpleasant to insect pests (Curry and Schmidt, 2007; Pant *et al.*, 2009). Various treatment techniques utilizing vermicompost, such as solid application, aqueous soil drench, and foliar spray, have been effective in controlling pests like aphids, mealybugs, and spider mites (Arancon *et al.*, 2005, 2007).

2.6. Response of Legume Crops to Rhizobium Inoculations

The way that Rhizobium inoculation affects legume crops varies on the kind of soil, the cultivar used, and the potency of the Rhizobium strains. According to reports, Rhizobium inoculation can supplement up to 80 kg N ha⁻¹ and boost pea plants' average output compared to uninoculated plants (Ahmed *et al.*, 2007).

Plant height, the number of branches, root and shoot dry weight, the number of nodules, seed, and biomass output, the number of pods, the crude protein concentration, and seed P content are all favorably impacted by Rhizobium inoculation (Murat *et al.*, 2009). In India, increasing nodulation and activating the nitrogenase enzyme in the root nodules to fix more atmospheric nitrogen was achieved by inoculating peas with Rhizobium leguminosarum at a dose of 20 g kg⁻¹ seed (Peoples M B, Ladha J K, *et al* 1995).

When compared to non-inoculated crops, the seed yields of lentil crops in Canada with rhizobia inoculants increased by 15% to 45% (Gan *et al.*, 2002). In Ethiopia, two root nodules from various regions of the country were used in recent investigations on the taxonomic and symbiotic features of field pea rhizobia (Kassa *et al.*, 2015). In Ethiopia, the number of pods per plant grew from 7 to 13.08 and the number of nodules per plant increased by 82 percent as compared to uninoculated plants. The weight of the hundred seeds increased by 11.44 percent (Bezabih, 2018).

When compared to treatments that weren't inoculated with Rhizobium, inoculated seeds weighed more per hundred seeds (28.76 g) (Endrias, 2017). It is generally established that inoculating legumes with a particular strain of rhizobium can increase N₂ fixation, plant output, and seed quality (Abera, 2015). According to Habtamu *et al.* (2017), the highest plant height was achieved when NP fertilizer and Rhizobium inoculation were applied together. Additionally, it was discovered by Raza *et al.* (2004) and Sajid *et al.* (2011) that Rhizobium inoculation raised the plant height of ground nuts and mung beans, respectively.

In a study by Otieno *et al.* (2007) inoculation with *Rhizobium* increased the number of nodules and nodule dry weight in beans and other legume species under study, but this did not translate into increased shoot or root dry matter and yield. They attributed this to the possible existence of more effective indigenous *Rhizobium* in the soil than the inoculants strains. While a study by Rabbanietal. (2005) on the effect of *Rhizobium* inoculation, N, P and Mn on nodulation, yield, and seed protein in pea showed that inoculated plants added 80 kg N/ha, and the average dry matter yield increased in pea plants over un-inoculated control.

Other studies have also reported that significant increases in pod yield, seed yield and protein content were obtained by *Rhizobium* inoculation (Tolkachev *et al.*, 1994). However, plants relying on fixed N for growth may achieve only 80-90% of the yield possible with N fertilization (Silsbury, 1979; Thies *et al.*, 1995). Also according to Cheminingwa *et al.*, (2007), *Rhizobia* inoculation and starter-N did not significantly improve shoot biomass per plant in common bean.

2.7. Biological Nitrogen Fixation in Legumes

Common beans, like other legumes, have the unique ability to convert atmospheric nitrogen into a usable form through a mutually beneficial relationship with a type of bacteria called rhizobium (Coskan and Dogan, 2011). Unlike rhizobium, which cannot perform nitrogen fixation independently, the bacteria rely on a symbiotic association with the roots of legume plants to carry out this process.

These bacteria use an enzyme called nitrogenase to fix atmospheric nitrogen where they are found around root hair. Rhizobia utilize plant resources for their reproduction after this mutualistic symbiosis has been formed, while fixed atmospheric nitrogen is used to satisfy the nitrogen needs of both the Rhizobia and the host plants. Ecological and financial benefits come from biological nitrogen fixation as a source of nitrogen (Ndakidemi *et al.*, 2006).

Bean's importance and uniqueness are due to its capacity to fix N_2 and form nodules along with a high proportion of protein (Wilcox and Shibles, 2001). N_2 fixation is influenced by a variety of factors during the formation and emergence of root hairs, including the density and presence of nodulating bacteria in the root zone, physical and chemical characteristics of the soil, such as humidity, temperature, and salt concentration, pH levels, and deficiencies of several mineral nutrients (Abdul-Jabbar and Saud, 2012). It is widely known that the nitrogen fixation rate is decreased when legumes are grown in soils with a lot of accessible nitrogen (Solomon *et al.*, 2012). The inhibitory effect of nitrate causes the reduction of capillary root development as well as prevents particular infection strands, indicating a shift from symbiotic to inorganic N nutrition (Coskan and Dogan, 2011).

In the biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) process, soil microorganisms work with nitrogen gas (N₂) from the atmosphere to integrate it into the tissue of legume plants. A unique structure known as nodules is created as a result of this symbiotic connection.

In exchange for reduced carbon (C) from the plant host to the microsymbiont, which is the rhizobia bacteria, the bacterial microsymbiont fixes nitrogen for the macrosymbiont, which is the legume plant (Gyaneshwar *et al.*, 2002). Complex mechanisms are required for the symbiosis to take place, beginning with the exchange of diffusible signal molecules (Ndakidemi and Dakora, 2003). Additionally, legume plants emit chemicals in their seeds and roots, primarily flavonoids, which some particular rhizobia species can detect (Makoi and Ndakidemi, 2013).

In exchange, rhizobia release a lipochitooligosachiride known as a nod factor, which acts as recognized receptors like the kinase of the legumes. The nodule then develops on the roots and helps the bacteria fix nitrogen (Santos *et al.*, 2013).

By increasing soil resources and crop productivity while lowering external nitrogen inputs and increasing the quality of soil resources, biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) reduces the need for mineral fertilizers, which may be expensive and inaccessible to smallholder farmers (Massawe *et al.*, 2016). In this aspect, legume crops like common beans show potential.

2.8. Methods of Quantifying Biological Nitrogen Fixation

Quantifying biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) is crucial for understanding its role in ecosystems and agricultural practices. Here are some major methods, along with recent citations:

Direct measurement methods:

- **Acetylene Reduction Assay (ARA):** This classic method measures the reduction of acetylene to ethylene by nitrogenase, a key enzyme in BNF. While invasive and require specialized equipment, it remains widely used (Jochum *et al.*, 2023).
- **Isotopic Acetylene Reduction Assay (ISARA):** A modification of ARA, ISARA analyzes the carbon stable isotope fraction between ethylene and acetylene to distinguish BNF by different nitrogenase isoforms. This helps determine the contribution of Mo-independent forms like vanadium and iron-only nitrogenases (Wang *et al.*, 2022).
- **Xylem-Solute Method:** This non-destructive technique estimates BNF by measuring the transport of ureides, nitrogenous compounds produced by nitrogen-fixing organisms, through the plant's xylem sap. Recent advances involve real-time measurements using online probes (Milla, 2023).

Indirect measurement methods:

- **Nitrogen Isotope Dilution Technique:** This method uses enriched ^{15}N isotopes to trace the fate of fixed N in the plant-soil system. It offers a whole-plant perspective but requires careful design and analysis (Hardarson, 2018).
- **Total Nitrogen Difference (TND) Method:** This approach compares the total nitrogen content of a legume crop grown with and without BNF to estimate the amount of fixed N. It's simple but has limitations due to soil N dynamics and other factors (Gómez-Vargas *et al.*, 2020).

- **Leaf Reflectance Spectroscopy:** This emerging method uses optical sensors to measure plant N concentration and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, providing a rapid and non-destructive way to estimate BNF, although further validation is needed (Nunes *et al.*, 2023).

Choosing the best method depends on factors like research objectives, plant type, experimental conditions, and resource availability. A combination of approaches can provide a more comprehensive understanding of BNF.

2.9. Rhizobium Inoculants

Selected strains of advantageous soil microorganisms are cultivated in a lab and packaged with or without a carrier as Rhizobium inoculants. They are a cost-effective, host-specific, and sustainable source of nitrogen (EIAR, 2016). Before planting, rhizobia inoculants applied to legume seeds increase the growth and yield of the crop as well as provide organic carbon and nitrogen for following or related crops (Fact sheet, 2016). Rhizobia inoculant-coated seeds are protected against chemical nitrogen fertilizer. The covered seeds must be planted as soon as possible in moist soil (EIAR, 2016). Maintaining or raising soil nitrogen levels through fixation, rhizobium inoculants increase soil fertility.

Legume crops can fix atmospheric nitrogen through Rhizobium bacteria in their root nodules, which may ease the demand for farmers to apply nitrogenous fertilizers to their crops. (Stagnari, F.*et al* 2017).

Adding pulses to the crop rotation helps to enhance the amount of organic matter in the soil (Abraham, 2015). Rhizobia inoculants can assist in increasing soil fertility levels for crops grown in the same area by being used continuously in cropping systems.

Therefore, the method is beneficial for Ethiopian soils, of which 85% reported having low amounts of nitrogen (EIAR, 2016).

The following are some ways that rhizobia inoculants help increase field crop production and productivity: - Increases yield by up to 10% (especially with 100 kg DAP/hectare) in any cropping system, by Improving soil health, increasing plant growth-promoting enzymes, hormones, and auxins (Fact sheet, 2016).

The choice of a Rhizobium strain that is especially suited to a certain host plant is crucial. The only approach to maximize nitrogen fixation and yields of leguminous crops is to carefully match Rhizobium strains with host plants and employ large viable inoculates made with this organism (Stajković, O. *et al* 2011).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Description of the Study Area

The experiment was carried out during the main rainy season (June to November) in 2022 at Maskan District, located 136 km southwest of Addis Ababa. The geographical location is latitude $8^{\circ}0'0''\text{N}$ and $8^{\circ}10'0''\text{N}$, east longitude $38^{\circ}10'0''$, $38^{\circ}20'0''$ to $38^{\circ}30'0''$ and altitude 1820-1836 m.a.s.l. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Map of the study area

The range of annual rainfall is 750 mm to 850 mm. The main rainy season is from June to September. The average maximum and minimum temperatures are 25.6°C and 10.34°C, respectively. The main soil textural classes in the study area are clay loam. Common bean was produced mainly next to maize in Maskan District (Maskan BOA, 2019).

3.2. Vermicompost sampling and analysis

Vermicompost was obtained from wondo genet woreda, lemelem vermicompost Enterprise. The product was prepared from fruit and vegetables scraps, coffee husks and well- aged manure. A composite sample that represents the entire vermicompost pile or production area was taken and analyzed for Selected Physico-chemical Properties.

The pH was determined using a 1:5 water suspension method, and a pH meter was employed. Organic carbon content of vermicompost was analyzed using the wet digestion method, as outlined by Walkley and Black (1934). Total nitrogen was analyzed using the Kjeldahl method, based on the work of Sahlemeden and Taye (2000). Available phosphorus was determined using the Olsen method, as described by Olsen *et al.* (1954).

The result displayed a pH of 8.14 and an electrical conductivity of 2.91 dS m⁻¹, indicating a strongly alkaline nature. The high nutrient content can be attributed to the diverse farmyard materials used in the composting process. Additionally, the vermicompost exhibited a favorable C: N ratio of 13.71, which promotes nutrient availability in the soil.

The available phosphorus in the vermicompost was found to be 642.8 mg/kg, which may be a result of increased bacterial and phosphatase activities during vermicomposting. Furthermore, the vermicompost showed higher levels of macro and micronutrients compared to ordinary compost, highlighting its potential impact on soil fertility and crop growth.

Table 1: physico-chemical properties of vermicompost

Parameters	Value
pH H₂O (1:5)	8.14
EC(dsm-1)	2.91
TN (%)	0.93
OC (%)	12.45
P (mg/kg)	642.8
C:N	13.41
CEC (cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	57.18
MC (%)	39.2

3.3. Soil sampling and analysis

A composite soil sample was taken from three representative areas in the field before sowing and prepared for physical and chemical analysis.

Post-harvest soil sampling was typically done after the harvest, 36 samples were collected by using auger. Samples were collected from the 0-30 cm depth of soil. And the soil samples were sent to a laboratory for analysis.

The soil texture was determined using the Bouyoucos hydrometer method (Bouyoucos, 1962). To determine the pH of the soil, a 1:2.5 water suspension method was used, and a pH meter was employed. Organic carbon was analyzed using the wet digestion method, as outlined by Walkley and Black (1934). This method involves digesting the organic carbon in the samples with potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$) in a sulfuric acid solution.

Total nitrogen was analyzed using the Kjeldahl method, based on the work of Sahlemeden and Taye (2000). This method involves treating the soil with concentrated sulfuric acid to oxidize the organic matter, converting the nitrogen in the organic nitrogenous compounds into ammonium sulfate during the oxidation process.

Available phosphorus was determined using the Olsen method, as described by Olsen *et al.* (1954). The method involves extracting available phosphorus and measuring its absorbance using a spectrophotometer after color development.

Bulk density was determined by selecting representative areas within the soil profile and using a soil corer to collect soil cores from the desired depth range. The corer has a known volume, mass of the soil core was measured using a field balance, and the bulk density was calculated by dividing the mass of the soil core by its known volume (Blake and Hartge, 1986). To account for spatial variability, multiple soil cores were collected at different plots within the study area.

Table 2: Selected Physical-chemical properties of the experimental soil before sowing.

Properties	value	Rating	Reference
Depth (cm)	0-30		
Physical properties			
Sand (%)	26		
Silt (%)	30		
Clay (%)	44		
Textural class	Clay		
Bulk density (g /cm ³)	1.42	Moderate	
Chemical Properties			
pH (H ₂ O)	5.56	Moderate Acidic	Tekalign, 1991
ECe(ds/m)	0.520		
Organic Matter (%)	1.84	Low	Tekalign, 1991
Organic carbon (%)	1.07	Low	Tekalign, 1991
Total N (%)	0.092	Low	Tekalign, 1991
Available P(mg/kg)	5.77	Very low	Sahlemedhinnd (2002)
CEC (cmol(+)/kg)	20	Moderate	Hazelton and Murphy, 2007

3.4. Determination of soil moisture content

Soil samples were taken at the 0-30 cm depth by core sampler. Each wet soil sample was weighted after collection and then the soil container was placed in the oven at 105°C for 24-48 hours.

After dried, samples were cooled down in a desiccator or a dry, cool place to prevent moisture absorption (Anon, 1990). This process was repeated for three times within the season (at 30, 60, and 90 days after planting). After having the weights of the wet and dry soil samples, the moisture content was calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = (\text{Wet weight} - \text{Dry weight}) / \text{Dry weight} * 100$$

3.5. Seed inoculation

Carrier-based inoculants of each strain were applied at the rate of 10 g inoculants per kg of seed (Rice *et al.*, 2001). The inoculants were mixed with sugar with the addition of some water to facilitate the adhesion of the strain on the seed. To ensure that the applied inoculants stick to the seed, 500 g/ha required quantities of inoculants were suspended in a 1:1 ratio in 10% sugar solution. The thick slurry of the inoculants was gently mixed with the dry seeds so that all the seeds received a thin coating of the inoculants.

To maintain the viability of the cells, inoculation was done under the shade and allowed to air dry for 30 minutes and sown at the recommended spacing. Seeds were immediately covered with soil after sowing to avoid the death of cells due to the sun's radiation. A plot with un-inoculated seeds was planted first to avoid contamination.

3.6. Variety selection

Selection of varieties was based on farmer preference. SER-125 was selected as the priority variety while at one station SER-125 ranked higher and yielded than other varieties with an average yield of 3.7 t ha⁻¹(Addis *et al.*, 2018). Hawassa Dume is high yielded and adapted in the study area.

Common bean varieties Hawassa Dume and SER-125 were planted in the main season (June-July). Two seeds per hill were planted. Finally, the seedlings were maintained into one seedling per hill by thinning the diseased and weak ones.

3.7. Treatments and Experimental Design

The treatments consisted of two varieties of common bean (Hawassa Dume and SER-125), three VC levels (0, 4, and 8 t ha⁻¹), and *Rhizobium* (inoculation and uninoculation). The experiment was laid out in RCB design with factorial arrangement and replicated three times per treatment.

The total treatment combination was 12 (3 x 2 x 2). The size of each plot was 3.2 m x 2.0 m (6.4 m²), plots and blocks are at distances of 1 m and 0.5 m apart. There were 8 rows spaced 40 cm in each plot and the intra-row plant spacing was 10 cm, Plants that grew in the outermost row on each side of the plot as well as those at each end of the rows are not used for data collection to avoid edge or border effects, one row next to the border rows was used for destructive sampling, the net plot area was 3.6 m².

For estimation of biological nitrogen fixation, as reference crop wheat was sown at the same time with common bean, at the boarder of blocks, there were 8 rows spaced 20 cm in plots.

Treatment Combination

Table 3: Treatment combination

Treatment	VC(t/ha)	Rhizobium	Varieties	Treatment combination
1	0	Inoculated	Hawassa Dume	+RH+0 VC+Hawassa Dume
2	0	Inoculated	SER-125	+RH+0 VC+ SER125
3	0	Un-inoculated	Hawassa Dume	-RH+0VC+ Hawassa Dume
4	0	Un-inoculated	SER-125	-RH+0VC+SER-125
5	4	Inoculated	Hawassa Dume	+RH+4 VC+Hawassa Dume
6	4	Inoculated	SER-125	+RH+4VC+Hawassa Dume
7	4	Un-inoculated	Hawassa Dume	-RH+4VC+Hawassa dume
8	4	Un-inoculated	SER-125	+RH+4VC+SER-125
9	8	Inoculated	Hawassa Dume	+RH+8 VC+Hawassa Dume
10	8	Inoculated	SER-125	+RH+8 VC+ SER125
11	8	Un-inoculated	Hawassa Dume	-RH+8VC+Hawassa dume
12	8	Un-inoculated	SER-125	-RH+8VC+SER-125

3.8. Experimental Procedures and Management

- **Cultural practices**

The experimental field was ploughed to get a fine seedbed using an oxen plow and the plots were leveled manually. Rows were made across each plot.

- **Time and method of fertilizer application**

Vermicompost was applied using the specified rates by mixing it with the soil at the time of sowing at the rate of 0, 4, and 8 t/ha.

3.9. Data collected

Agronomic parameters

- **Days to flowering:** It was recorded as the number of days from sowing to the time when 50% of the plants in each plot show first flower.
- **Plant height (cm):** It was recorded from 10 randomly selected plants per plot just before harvest from the base of the plant to the tip of the main stem and was expressed as height per plant.
- **Number of branches per Plant:** It was counted from the main stems of 10 randomly selected plants of the four central rows and expressed as the number of branches per plant
- **Number of Pods per plant:** The total pods in 10 randomly selected plants in each plot were counted at the time of harvest and expressed as the number of pods per plant.
- **Number of seeds per pod:** In the above-counted pods the total seeds were counted and averaged to determine the number of seeds per pod.
- **Seed weight (g):** Thousand seeds were counted from harvested bulk of each plot and their weight was recorded and adjusted at 10% moisture content.
- **Above ground biomass (kg):** It was taken at physiological maturity after harvesting plants from all pots of the respective treatments close to the ground surface. The harvested plants were oven dried to constant weight at 60 °C and weighed using a sensitive balance to determine the above ground biomass yield per plant.

- **Grain yield (kg):** This was recorded from each net plot area (3.6 m²). The moisture content was determined for yield harvested from the net plot area and adjusted to the standard moisture content of pulses (10%).
- **Harvest Index:** Harvest index per pot was recorded as the ratio of the grain yield to the yield of the aboveground biomass.

Nodulation Parameters

- **Nodulation:** Five bean plants were randomly taken to count and weight nodules. The soil around the roots was dug to loosen and the plants were uprooted carefully. The muddy roots were washed in a bucket where the nodules were easily seen.
- **Effective number of nodules (number):** The nodules were separated by their colors and splitting them by cutting of pocket knife shows a pink to dark-red color indicating effective nodules, whereas a green color indicates non-effective nodulation.
- **Nodule dry weight (g plant⁻¹):** The nodules were collected from five plant samples from each plot the nodules were placed at 70°C for 24 hrs in an oven to dry them to constant weights to determine nodule dry weight per plant.

Estimation of biological nitrogen fixation

The TND method was used to estimate BNF rates of common beans. Because of the TND method has several advantages over other methods for estimating biological nitrogen fixation (BNF).

1. Simplicity and ease of implementation:

The TND method is conceptually straightforward and doesn't require complex equipment or specialized laboratories. Only need to measure the total nitrogen content of fixing and non-fixing plants (controls) grown under similar conditions.

This makes it accessible to researchers with limited resources and can be implemented in field settings without advanced technical expertise (Bado *et al.*, 2018)

2. Cost-effectiveness:

Compared to methods like Isotopic Dilution (ID), which require expensive isotopes and specialized analysis, the TND method is significantly cheaper. This makes it more feasible for large-scale studies and practical field applications (Bado *et al.*, 2018).

3. Rapidity and efficiency:

The TND method is quicker than some other approaches, like the Acetylene Reduction Assay (ARA), which often require extended measurement periods. This allows for faster data collection and analysis, especially in field trials (Bado *et al.*, 2018).

4. Useful for initial BNF assessments and field screening:

Although TND might not be the most accurate method, it can still provide valuable first approximations of BNF activity. This can be useful for initial screening of different legume genotypes or assessing the general impact of agricultural practices on BNF (Bado *et al.*, 2018).

Based on the above selected method, prior to full maturity, bean plant samples were collected from each plot using 1.5 m² quadrats. Both beans and the reference crop (wheat) were harvested, labeled, and dried in an oven at 70°C for 48 hours. Dry matter of each sample was then measured using a precise balance (Sahlemeden & Taye, 2000).

- **Total Nitrogen Analysis:** Samples were crushed and sieved to pass through a 1mm sieve. Total nitrogen analysis followed the Kjeldahl method (Sahlemeden & Taye, 2000). This method employs specific equipment like burettes, pipettes, 250ml Erlenmeyer flasks, a magnetic stirrer, and 300ml Kjeldahl flasks. The Kjeldahl procedure relies on the principle that treating plant material with concentrated, oxidized sulfuric acid converts organic nitrogen into ammonium sulfate. Ammonia released during distillation with NaOH is then trapped by an acid solution. After adsorption as NH₄⁺ ions in boric acid, the ammonia is back-titrated with standardized H₂SO₄ (Unkovich *et al.*, 2008).
- **Calculating Nitrogen Yield and BNF:** Nitrogen yield was calculated by multiplying the nutrient N concentration by the dry matter yield of the beans, as described by Unkovich *et al.*, (2008). Finally, biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) was estimated using the N difference method.
- **N Difference Method and its Assumption:** This method, calculates the difference in N accumulated between N₂-fixing and non-fixing plants. It assumes that both types of plants take up the same amount of soil mineral N, provided they have comparable rooting depths.

The following equations were used.

N Fixed = N –yield fixing plant – N-yield reference plant (Unkovich *et al.*, 2008).

%Ndfa = 100(TNf – TN ref) / TNf (Bliss and and Hardson, 1993)

Where: %Ndfa is the nitrogen derived from the atmosphere and N-yield is the total nitrogen accumulated in both the fixing and non-fixing plants.

TNf is the total N-content of fixing plants and **TN ref** is the total N-content of reference crop.

3.10. Data analysis

Data collected was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) appropriate to the factorial experiment in RCBD according to the General Linear Model (GLM) procedure of SAS version 9.4 (SAS Institute, 2004) and interpretations were following the procedure described by Gomez and Gomez (1984). When the effects of the treatments are found significant from the ANOVA test, the means are compared using the least significance difference (LSD) test at a 5% level of significance.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Effect of Vermicompost, Rhizobium, and Varieties of Common Bean on Soil Physico-Chemical Properties after Harvesting.

4.1.1. Bulk Density

The analysis of variance showed that there was no significant difference in the main effect and interaction effect on the bulk density of soil. Bulk Density values did not differ significantly within treatments. Overall, the lack of significant differences in bulk density values within treatments suggests that the factors tested in the study did not strongly influence soil compaction or density under the experimental conditions.

Changes in bulk density often occur gradually over time in response to long-term management practices or environmental factors (Eftene, A. *et al.*, 2020). The duration of this study was relatively short; it might not capture significant changes in bulk density resulting from the treatments.

4.1.2. Soil pH

Soil pH greatly affects several important processes including the activity of soil microorganisms and the availability of nutrients to plants. The analysis of variance showed that there were non-significant differences in soil pH values between the different levels of organic applied and rhizobium on common bean varieties.

Soil pH ranged from 5.78 to 5.92 across the whole experimental plot, showing that the application of organic on common bean varieties did not influence the soil pH significantly.

These may be due to the short duration of the field experiment. The pH values observed in the plot with the maximum level of treatment combination were within the range of moderately acid soil reaction as indicated by Tekalign (1991). Similarly, Tesfaye *et al.*, (2020) also reported application of organic fertilizer residuals did not influence the soil pH significantly.

4.1.3. Electrical Conductivity (ECe)

The electrical conductivity (ECe) measurement identifies potentially saline soils (Okalebo *et al.*, 2002). The analysis of variance showed that the main effect of vermicompost, ($p < 0.001$) had significant effects on electrical Conductivity (ECe). However, the main effect of *Rhizobium* and variety, the two-factor interaction and three factor interaction had no significant effect on electrical Conductivity (ECe) of the soil.

The treatment that received 8 t/ha vermicompost resulted (0.722 ds m^{-1}) whereas; control plots (0.546 ds m^{-1}). (Table 4) These soil is generally low in soluble salts and are not prone to salinity issues (Brady, N.C., & Weil, R.R., 2019).

The addition of vermicompost to low salinity soils can improve soil fertility, structure, and microbial activity, leading to healthier and more productive growing conditions for plants Lim, S. L., *et al* (2015). As well as vermicompost is generally low in soluble salts compared to many other organic amendments. When vermicompost is added to soil, it can help dilute the concentration of soluble salts present in the soil solution. As a result, the overall EC of the soil was low (Zaman, M. *et al.*, 2018).

Table 4: The main effects of VC on ECe, organic carbon, total nitrogen and CEC

Treatment	Ece (ds /m)	OC(%)	TN(%)	CEC(cmol+ kg-1)
VC(t/ha)				
0	0.546 ^c	1.15 ^c	0.09 ^c	21.83 ^c
4	0.548 ^b	1.27 ^b	0.11 ^b	24.75 ^b
8	0.722 ^a	1.46 ^a	0.12 ^a	26.08 ^a
P-value	**	**	**	**
LSD^{0.05}	0.033	0.06	0.005	1.2871
CV (%)	6.56	5.34	5.34	6.31

Similar letters or no letters within the column indicate that there is no significant difference among treatment levels, $\alpha = 0.05$, based on the LSD test. CV= Coefficient of variation, VC= vermicompost. , Ece= Electrical Conductivity, OC=Organic carbon, TN= Total nitrogen, CEC= Cation exchange capacity.

4.1.4. Organic Carbon (OC)

The main effects of vermicompost had significantly increased soil organic carbon (Table 4). In another way the main effect of Rhizobium and variety two and three factor interaction did not affect this parameter. The highest (1.46%) soil OC was obtained from the application of 8 t/ha vermicompost, while the lowest (1.15%) was recorded for soil from the control plots (Table 4).

This improvement might be because of vermicompost is organic in nature and originally rich in organic carbon content. On the other hand, worms increased organic carbon in the cast because of selective feeding on non humified material within the soil matrix and secretion of mucopolysaccharide in their gut. The results were similar to those presented by Singh *et al.*, (2007), Anwar *et al.*, (2005) and Yagi *et al.*, (2003).

The findings of a similar study indicated that the application of organic fertilizer significantly improved soil organic carbon from 1.26% to 1.56% (Girma *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, Alemayehu (2017) reported an average organic carbon content of each treatment after harvesting was 8.4% higher than the initial organic carbon content of the soil at Bako. Tigist *et a.*, (2019) reported vermicompost application at rate of 4.50t/ha on soybean showed significance improvement in soil organic carbon at Asosa, western Ethiopia.

4.1.5. Total Nitrogen (TN)

The main effect of vermicompost highly and significantly ($P < 0.001$) affected the total nitrogen of the soil (Table 4). In another way the main effect of Rhizobium and variety, two and three factor interaction did not affect this parameter. Total nitrogen, which is a primary nutrient that limits the growth of most crops, was in the range of 0.09 to 0.12% after the application of different rates of vermicompost.

The soil's total nitrogen reached its highest level (0.12%) in plots treated with 8 t/ha of vermicompost, while the lowest nitrogen content (0.09%) was found in the control plot. This represented 33 % increase in total nitrogen compared to the control. Similar findings reported by Berhanu (1980), where soil total nitrogen levels varied between control plots and those treated with 6 t/ha of vermicompost. This outcome is likely due to the organic matter present in vermicompost, which decomposes through the action of earthworms. During decomposition, nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, among other nutrients, become more accessible to plants as they are released from the decomposed organic material.

As well as the presence of earthworms in vermicompost enhances soil microbial activity, microbes facilitate the breakdown of organic matter and help convert nitrogen into forms that plants can absorb. This increased microbial activity enhances nitrogen availability in the soil. Vermicompost also aids in the formation of humus, which is a stable organic material that retains moisture, improves soil structure, and enhances nutrient retention, including nitrogen. This contributes to a more balanced and sustainable nitrogen supply for plants (Pathma J, Sakthivel N. 2012).

Moreover, vermicompost helps mitigate nitrogen loss from the soil through leaching and volatilization. The organic matter in vermicompost acts as a sponge, absorbing excess nitrogen and preventing it from being washed away by water or lost to the atmosphere as gases (Masciandaro *et al.*, 2010). Overall, using vermicompost as an organic fertilizer can enhance nitrogen levels in the soil, and fostering healthier plant growth.

4.1.6. Cation Exchangeable Capacity (CEC)

The main effects of vermicompost highly significantly ($P < 0.001$) influenced by the cation exchangeable capacity of the soil (Table 4). While the main effect of Rhizobium and variety, two and three factor interaction did not affect this parameter.

Accordingly, the highest CEC ($26.08 \text{ cmol}^+ \text{ kg}^{-1}$) was obtained from the application of 8 t/ha vermicompost, while the lowest CEC value was recorded from the control plots (0 t/ha VC) (Table 4). Whereas, the highest CEC values of soil could be due to increased organic matter content, which had a strong influence on CEC.

Organic matter contains negatively charged functional groups that can attract and hold onto positively charged cations. As a result, the addition of vermicompost can increase the CEC of the soil (Oorts *et al.*, 2003).

Vermicompost contains humic and fulvic acids, which are intricate organic compounds formed through the breakdown of plant and animal remains. These substances have a strong attraction to positively charged ions and can create stable bonds with them, effectively enhancing the soil's Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC).

The rise in CEC facilitated by vermicompost enables the soil to retain more nutrients, thereby increasing their availability for plant absorption. This contributes to improved soil fertility and nutrient accessibility for plants. Additionally, vermicompost enhances soil structure by promoting the formation of aggregates and increasing pore space. This allows for better water penetration and root growth, leading to improved nutrient exchange and CEC. Incorporating vermicompost into soil elevates its CEC by introducing organic matter and humic substances. This augmentation of CEC proves advantageous for soil fertility. Correspondingly, Tolanur (2002) noted a significant increase in cation exchange capacity with higher rates of organic fertilizer application, supporting these findings.

These results were in agreement with Abosedera *et al.*, (2015) and Hossein *et al.*, (2014) who mentioned that the addition of vermicompost to the soil could reach the exchange capacity to 200 C mole Kg⁻¹ and increase the activity of microorganisms that decompose organic matter worked to increase soil CEC. Tamado and Mitiku (2017) observed improvement in Cation exchange capacity as a result of increased rates of vermicompost application.

4.1.7. Available Phosphorus

Soil available P is the most common plant growth-limiting nutrient in tropical soils next to N. The main effects of vermicompost and *Rhizobium* significantly influenced available phosphorus P in soil. (Table 5) On the contrary, the main effect of variety, the two-factor of *Rhizobium* x variety, and three-factor interactions did not significantly affect the available phosphorus. On the other hand, the two factors of vermicompost x *Rhizobium* had a significant effect on this soil parameter. Concentration of available P in the soil after applying vermicompost and *Rhizobium* fertilizer ranges from 6.70 to 13.95 mg/ kg.

The highest value (13.95 mg/kg) was obtained from treatment applied 8 t ha⁻¹ VC+ seed inoculated by HP-429 strain followed by treatment applied 4 t ha⁻¹VC+Non inoculated seed (8.98 mg/kg). The lowest 6.70 mg/kg was obtained from the control plot (0 t ha⁻¹VC + non-inoculated seed). (Table 5)

The value of available P before planting was lower as compared to the values after harvest. This implies that available P levels in plots that received fertilizer were slightly higher than that of the control (no application). EthioSIS (2014) suggested the optimum P content for most Ethiopian soil as 15 ppm. Based on this, the available phosphorous content of the soil of the study area is optimum for the highest rate of fertilizer. This may be due to a high interaction between vermicompost and *Rhizobium* can lead to synergistic effects on soil phosphorus availability and plant growth.

When combined, vermicompost creates conditions that support Rhizobium colonization and activity, leading to improved nitrogen fixation and subsequent plant absorption of phosphorus. Ansari and Ismail (2012) evaluated that the presence of organic matter and microbial activity in vermicompost aids in enhancing soil structure, water retention, and nutrient cycling, which further boosts phosphorus availability and plant uptake. These microbes contribute to the breakdown of organic matter and the release of nutrients, including phosphorus, from organic forms to mineral forms that are more readily available to plants.

Both vermicompost and rhizobium play crucial roles in nutrient cycling within the soil ecosystem. Vermicompost provides a continuous supply of organic matter and nutrients, which serves as a substrate and energy source for soil microorganisms, including rhizobium. In return, rhizobium fix atmospheric nitrogen, which can stimulate microbial activity and enhance the breakdown of organic phosphorus compounds, making phosphorus more available to plants (Oyege, I., *et al* 2023)..

The combined use of vermicompost and rhizobium enhances plant health and vitality. Rhizobium bacteria are essential for nitrogen fixation, a process crucial for protein synthesis and overall plant growth. Strong-rooted, healthy plants are more efficient at absorbing nutrients, including phosphorus. Moreover, the presence of rhizobium enhances plant resistance to environmental stresses, thus optimizing phosphorus utilization. Vermicompost regulates soil pH, providing conditions favorable for rhizobium survival and activity. Certain rhizobium strains are sensitive to acidic environments, and vermicompost's buffering capacity helps maintain an optimal pH range conducive to rhizobium colonization and nitrogen fixation. This indirectly improves phosphorus availability and absorption by plants.

These results were agree with the findings of Aung *et al.*, (2010),and Mahmoud *et al.*, (2016).This finding was in agreement with Getachew and Tilahun (2017) who reported that addition of organic residues contributed to the desorption of phosphate and thus improved the available P content in soil. Similarly, Arthur (2009) also reported that increased in application of vermicompost level substantially increased the availability and efficiency of phosphorus.

Table 5: Interaction effect vermicompost and Rhizobium on available P

Treatment	Available P	
V(t/ha)	<i>Rhizobium</i>	
	Inoculated	Un-inoculated
0	6.70 ^c	7.04 ^c
4	7.86 ^{bc}	8.98 ^b
8	13.95 ^a	8.92 ^b
P-value	**	
LSD ^{0.05}	1.46	
CV (%)	13.96	

Similar letters or no letters within the column indicate that there is no significant difference among treatment levels, $\alpha= 0.05$, based on the LSD test. CV= Coefficient of variation, VC=Vermicompost

4.2. Effect of Vermicompost on Moisture Content of the Soil.

The soil moisture content at 30 60 and 90 days of sampling was very highly significantly ($p < .0001$, $p < .0001$, $p < 0.0005$) affected by vermicompost application, whereas the main effects of Rhizobium and varieties and the interaction effects are non-significant.

Different levels of vermicompost resulted in different moisture content at different growing seasons of common beans, the data showed that at the establishment month (30 days), at the flowering stage (60 days) and at the physiological maturity stage (90 days) the rates of 8 t/ha VC recorded higher soil moisture content, while the minimum soil moisture content was recorded from control (0 t/ha VC) plots (Table 6). The plots that received a higher vermicompost rate could consume much soil moisture to give a higher crop biomass and vice versa for a lower vermicompost rate on soil moisture. All vermicomposts at high rates showed a positive impact on the soil water content at all stages of growth.

Variations of soil water profiles changed with time and were dependent on rainfall. Under different rates of vermicompost, soil water varied with the changes in precipitation patterns. Soil water of each plot presented higher soil moisture content during the peak of precipitation (August) 60 days and it gradually decreased downward at harvesting time (October) 90 days.

The outcome observed in this study aligns with Wakgari's findings (2021), which indicated a rise in soil moisture levels attributed to the application rate of vermicompost. Similarly, Tharmaraj *et al.*, (2011) noted the highest soil moisture content following vermicompost application.

This increase can be attributed to the presence of colloidal components in vermicompost, such as earthworm mucus and polysaccharides, which serve as water-absorbing agents and enhance the soil's water retention capacity. Furthermore, the burrowing activity of worms significantly influences water permeability in the soil. Vermi-casts, capable of storing water up to eight to nine times their weight, contribute to the soil's fertility enhancement (Munnoli and Bhosle, 2011; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2015).

Table 6: Effects of VC on soil moisture content

SMC (%)			
VC(t/ha)	30day	60 day	90 day
0	28.57 ^c	26.54 ^c	17.17 ^b
4	31.49 ^b	28.53 ^b	17.00 ^b
8	37.36 ^a	32.62 ^a	19.92 ^a
LSD^{0.05}	2.404	1.5482	1.4594
P value	**	**	**
CV (%)	8.79	6.26	9.61

Similar letters or no letters within the column indicate that there is no significant difference among treatment levels, $\alpha = 0.05$, based on the LSD test. CV= Coefficient of variation, VC=Vermicompost

Increased soil organic matter enhances the soil's ability to absorb water, leading to less water stress during both dry and wet periods. This can be achieved by: Incorporate compost, manures, or other stable organic materials. In this case Vermicompost improves the structure of the soil by filling in the porous spaces within the soil. This leads to more water being absorbed by the organic matter instead of escaping as run-off.

Organic fertilizers can increase the porosity and soil permeability of the plow layer, promote soil suppression and moisture retention, improve the water storage and water retention performance of the soil, and to a certain extent coordinate the impact between crop water demand and soil water supply, thereby improving fertilizer utilization efficiency and water use efficiency (Morugan-Coronado *et al.*, 2019).

4.3. Effect of Rhizobium Inoculation, Vermicompost Application and Varieties on Phenological and growth Parameters of common bean

4.3.1. Days to 50% Flowering

The analysis of variance revealed that the main effects of *Rhizobium*, vermicompost, and variety ($P < 0.01$) significantly influenced days to 50% flowering. Similarly, the two-factor interaction of vermicompost x *Rhizobium*, Vermicompost x variety, and *Rhizobium* x variety ($P < 0.01$), and three-factor interaction of vermicompost x *Rhizobium* x variety significantly ($P < 0.01$) were affected days to 50% flowering of the crop.

Thus, the interaction rate of vermicompost, *Rhizobium* inoculated with HP-429 strain and variety prolonged the days required to 50% flowering of the crop. The most prolonged duration to reach 50% flowering was observed in response to the combined application of organic, bio-fertilizer and Hawassa Dume common bean variety which means 8 t ha⁻¹ vermicompost + Hawassa Dume common bean variety inoculated with HP - 429 *Rhizobium* strain. (Table 7)

However, the minimum duration of 50% flowering was observed in the control treatments (nil) and SER -125 common bean variety. (Table 7) This may be attributed to the synergic effects of the organic and bio-fertilizers in promoting cell growth and prolonging vegetative growth.

The possible reason for delayed flowering with the *Rhizobium* inoculation might be because the inoculant improved nitrogen fixation and thus increased N uptake by plants and resulted in a prolonged time for vegetative growth of common beans thus leading to delayed flowering time. This result is in agreement with the finding of Tairo and Ndakidemi (2013) who reported that inoculation resulted in late flowering relative to the control in soybean both under greenhouse and field conditions.

As well as this might be due to vermicompost application which contained a greater amount of available N, Mg, Ca, P, K, and other nutrients which improved the vegetative growth of plants (Lim *et al.*, 2015). Aemiro (2020) have showed that Faba bean seed inoculated treatments had taken relatively longer days to reach 50% flowering than uninoculated treatments. Adane (2023) reported that the highest vermicompost rate had taken relatively longer days (63.00) days to reach 50% flowering of Faba bean than the control treatments (55.78)and inoculated treatments with Fb18 strain had taken relatively longer days (61.00) than uninoculated treatments (56.80 days).

It might be due to their genotype differences. In line with this result, Kilasi (2010) and Habtamu (2019) indicated differences in crop phenology due to the genetic makeup of the varieties or the environmental conditions existing during the growth and grain-filling period of the crop development.

Table 7: The interaction effects of vermicompost, Rhizobium, and varieties on days to 50% flowering

Treatments		50% Flowering (%)	
VC(t/ha)	Varieties	<i>Rhizobium</i>	
		Inoculated	Non inoculated
0	Hawassa Dume	37.00 ^f	36.00 ^g
	SER-125	37.00 ^f	35.00 ^h
4	Hawassa Dume	39.66 ^d	38.00 ^e
	SER-125	39.33 ^d	37.00 ^f
8	Hawassa Dume	45.00 ^a	41.00 ^e
	SER-125	42.00 ^b	41.00 ^e
P-value		**	
LSD^{0.05}		0.39	
CV (%)		0.63	

Interaction means within a columns followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different at $P > 0.05$; ns = non-significant; *** = significant at $P \leq 0.001$, ** significant at $P \leq 0.01$; CV= Coefficient of variation, VC= Vermicompost rates.

4.3.2. Plant Height (cm)

The analysis of variance illustrated that the main effect of vermicompost and *Rhizobium* ($P < 0.01$) was influenced plant height but varieties of common bean did not show a significant effect on plant height.

On the other hand, the two-factor interaction of vermicompost x variety and *Rhizobium* x variety, and the three-factor interaction of the *Rhizobium* x vermicompost x variety had no significant effects on the plant height of the crop. However, the effect of *Rhizobium* x vermicompost ($P < 0.05$) significantly influenced this parameter.

The highest number of plant height (87.58 cm) resulted from the application of 8 t/ha of vermicompost inoculated with *Rhizobium* HP-429 strain, which was followed by application of 8 t/ha of vermicompost with non-inoculated of common bean (80.4 cm) while the lowest height of plant (60.48 cm) was recorded in the control treatment. (Table 8) Plant height of common bean also increases with increasing vermicompost rate. (Table 8)

The results obtained here are in agreement with those of Gopinath *et al.* (2011) who revealed a significant increase in growth and yield by the organic input. This is through delivering greater amounts of available C, Mg, Ca, P, and K for the plant (Lim *et al.*, 2015).

In addition to the mineral nutrition content of vermicompost, further stimulates plant growth by enhancing beneficial microorganisms and the microbial-mediated release of phytohormones (Frankenberger and Arshad, 1997).

Probably it was due to N fixation encouraged by strains that play vital roles in the vegetative growth of common bean plants. The high availability of nutrients, especially nitrogen, stimulates growth and increases the length of internodes through increased plant height. The plant height as a result of the use of bio-fertilizers also increased due to better root development and uptake of water and nutrients and the production of growth hormones known as gibberellin acid and auxins (Nazeri *et al.*, 2012).

In agreement with this result, Anteneh and Abere (2017) reported a remarkable increase in plant height of faba bean. They revealed that increasing vermicompost application with the highest values recorded at 8 ton/ha than the inoculated (*Rhizobium* strain, HUFBR-15) and control.

Similarly, Azarpour, *et al* (2012) stated that the highest plant height (77.52cm) of soybean was recorded on the plot treated with a maximum rate of vermicompost with nitroxinbiofertilizer over control treatment. And Adane (2023) stated that the tallest (182.53 cm) mean plant height of Faba bean was recorded, in plots treated with vermicompost+ Fb18, while the shortest (119.40 cm) mean values of plant height was recorded from control. Also, Endalkachew *et al.*, (2019b) found that the highest plant height (59.33 cm) of faba bean was obtained in the pot that received 8 ton/ha FYM combined with *Rhizobium* inoculants than control and other treatments.

Table 8: Effects of vermicompost and Rhizobium on Plant height, vermicompost and varieties on number of primary branches

Plant Height(cm)			No. of Primary Branches		
Treatments		<i>Rhizobium</i>	Varieties		
VC(t/ha)	Inoculation	Non inoculated	VC(t/ha)	Hawassa Dume	SER-125
0	71.18 ^c	60.48 ^d	0	3.400 ^d	3.166 ^d
4	77.86 ^b	76.75 ^b	4	6.966 ^b	5.166 ^c
8	87.58 ^a	80.40 ^b	8	7.733 ^a	6.866 ^b
P-value		*	**		
LSD^{0.05}		4.496	0.761		
CV(%)		5.04	11.64		

*Interaction means within a columns followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different at $P > 0.05$; ns = non-significant; *** = significant at $P \leq 0.001$, ** significant at $P \leq 0.01$; CV= Coefficient of variation, VC= Vermicompost rates.*

4.3.3. Number of Primary Branches

The analysis of variance illustrated that the main effect of vermicompost, *Rhizobium*, and variety showed a significant ($P < 0.01$) influence on several primary branches. On the contrary, the two-factor interactions of vermicompost x *Rhizobium* and *Rhizobium* x variety, and the three-factor interaction of vermicompost x *Rhizobium* x variety had no significant influence on the number of primary branches. (Appendix Table 6) On the other hand, vermicompost x variety significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced the number of primary branches.

The maximum number of primary branches per plant was (7.73) produced by plants treated with 8 t/ha vermicompost applied on the Hawassa Dume common bean variety. The minimum number of branches per plant (3.16) was produced at the nil rate of vermicompost and SER 125 common bean variety. (Table 8)

The interaction effect may vary depending on their nutrient requirements and uptake capacities of varieties. So depends on that, Hawassa Dume varieties respond more positively to vermicompost application, resulting in increased primary branch development, while SER-125 may not exhibit significant changes.

The interaction effect of vermicompost application interacts with the genetic makeup of each variety to influence primary branch development. May vary depending on the specific environmental conditions in which the common bean varieties are grown.

Vermicompost and common bean varieties on primary branches may be mediated by changes in root architecture and hormone signaling pathways (Edwards 2006). Al-Tawarah.,*et al.*, (2024) was noted that all the rates of vermicompost increased it with a significant superiority in the treatment of VC100 (63.00), as in the case of rates of compost addition. Arancon, (2006) stated that vermicompost has a large particulate surface area that provides many micro-sites for microbial activities and for the strong retention of nutrients.

4.4. Effect of Rhizobium Inoculation, Vermicompost Application, and varieties on Nodulation and nitrogen fixation of common bean

4.4.1. Total Number of Nodules

The analysis of variance showed that the main effects of vermicompost, and *Rhizobium* significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced the total number of nodules produced per plant. However, the main effects of variety did not have significant effects on the total number of nodules. The two-factor interactions of vermicompost x variety and *Rhizobium* x variety significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) influenced the total number of nodules produced per plant. While the others interaction effects were not significant on this parameter of the plant. (Appendix Table 5)

The highest result was obtained from the application of *Rhizobium inoculation* applied on Hawassa Dume (37.09) but statistically similar to Rhizobium inoculation applied on SER-125 (35.67) common bean variety. Similarly, the maximum result was obtained from the application of 4 t/ha vermicompost on Hawassa Dume variety.

This might be because of genetic factors inherent in different common bean varieties could influence their nodulation capacity with *Rhizobium* bacteria. Certain varieties might naturally develop more nodules and exhibit superior compatibility with *Rhizobium* strains compared to others. Different bean varieties may respond diversely to these factors, resulting in varied nodulation outcomes.

The observed differences in nodulation parameters among the common bean varieties could be related to the inherent symbiosis characteristics of the varieties (Habtam, 2017). In line with this result, Tarekegn *et al.* (2017) found that the performance of five different varieties of cowpeas varied significantly for nodulation parameters. Dereje *et al.* (2015) reported that *Rhizobial* inoculations significantly increased the number of nodules per plant and symbiotic effectiveness as compared to the control treatments. The higher nodulation performance of the Hawassa Dume variety when inoculated with an effective bio-inoculant indicates its high biological N₂ fixing capacity (Hungria and Bohrer, 2000).

Table 9: Interaction effect of Rhizobium and Variety ,Vermicompost and variety treatments on number of nodules

Number of Nodules					
Treatments	Varieties		Varieties		
<i>Rhizobium</i>	Hawassa Dume	SER-125	VC(t/ha)	Hawassa Dume	SER-125
Inoculated	37.09 ^a	35.67 ^a	0	29.53 ^c	34.30 ^b
Un-Inoculated	31.20 ^b	33.98 ^{ab}	4	39.73 ^a	36.87 ^{ab}
			8	33.17 ^{ab}	33.3 ^{bc}
P-value	*		P-value	**	
LSD^{0.05}	3.98		LSD^{0.05}	4.07	
CV (%)	12.03		CV (%)	10.02	

*Interaction means within a columns followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different at $P > 0.05$; ns = non-significant; *** = significant at $P \leq 0.001$, ** significant at $P \leq 0.01$; CV= Coefficient of variation, VC= Vermicompost rates.*

Vermicompost and variety interaction had a significant influence on the number of nodules the maximum nodule numbers (39.73) were recorded from 4 t/ha vermicompost application on Hawassa Dume variety. Vermicompost has stuff like organic material and nutrients that make soil better and help tiny organisms in the soil, different types of common beans might react in different ways to the nutrients in vermicompost. This can affect how well they make nodules with bacteria that help with nitrogen in the soil. Put vermicompost on common bean plants, their roots grow better, which makes it easier for nodules to form.

Vermicompost also has good microorganisms that make the soil better. These tiny organisms can help common bean roots grow nodules, but different bean types might react to them in different ways. Melese (2020) stated that the highest nodule number (168.25) was recorded from snap bean plants treated with 45 t/ha vermicompost, least was recorded from the control, and the highest number of nodule (167.93) was recorded by snap bean variety BC4.4, followed by Faraday (138.083) and Plati (137.7) varieties,

The present study found a significant reduction of nodule number with 8-tonn ha⁻¹ vermicompost application on varieties. This could be because vermicompost contains relatively large amounts of N immediately available for plant uptake (Datta *et al.*, 2011) which may reduce the nodule initiation and development (Clayton *et al.*, 2004). Anteneh and Abere (2017) also reported similar result as a significant reduction of nodule number at 8 t/ha vermicompost application of faba bean. Similarly, Aemiro (2020) reported that similar result as a significant reduction of nodule number at 9 t/ha vermicompost application of faba bean.

4.4.2. Nodule Dry Weight (g/plant)

The analysis of variance demonstrated that the main effects of vermicompost and *Rhizobium* significantly ($P < 0.01$) affected nodule dry weight per plant. However, the main effects of variety did not have significant effects on nodule dry weight. Similarly, the two-factor interactions and three-factor interaction did not significantly affect the nodule dry weight of the crop. (Appendix Table 5)

Nodule dry weight per plant was significantly influenced by *Rhizobium* inoculated (Table 10). The highest nodule dry weight (0.1504 g/plant) was recorded from plots treated with *Rhizobium* inoculated, whereas the lowest nodule dry weight (0.1298 g/plant) was obtained from control plots (un inoculated).

The observed increase in nodule dry weight upon inoculation compared to the untreated control may be attributed to the well-known ability of rhizobia to convert atmospheric nitrogen into a form usable by plants. When rhizobia are present in the soil and effectively colonize the roots of common bean plants, they form nodules where nitrogen fixation takes place. Greater populations or more efficient strains of *Rhizobium* can lead to heightened nitrogen fixation and, consequently, increased nodule dry weights (Fahde, S., *et al.*, 2023).

Rhizobium establish a symbiotic relationship with leguminous plants like common beans, residing within nodules and supplying fixed nitrogen to the plant in exchange for carbohydrates. The presence of rhizobia and the establishment of this symbiotic relationship are essential for nodule formation and subsequent nitrogen fixation, directly impacting nodule dry weights, inoculation with rhizobia can stimulate nodule development on common bean plant roots, initiates and promotes nodule growth, serving as sites for nitrogen fixation. Elevated levels of rhizobia colonization or more effective strains can lead to a greater number and size of nodules, thereby contributing to increased nodule dry weights (Fahde, S., *et al.*, 2023).

Effective *Rhizobium* colonization and nitrogen fixation contribute to improved plant health and growth. Common bean plants with well-developed nodules and efficient nitrogen fixation systems often exhibit vigorous growth and development, which can lead to larger and more abundant nodules with higher dry weights.

This result corroborates woldesenbet.,(2021) the highest nodule dry weight (0.2383 g/plant) of faba bean was recorded from plots treated with Rhizobium inoculated with HP - 429 whereas the lowest nodule dry weight (0.1723 g/plant) was obtained from control plots (without inoculated). Workneh *et al.*, (2013) and Suryantini (2014) stated that the highest nodule dry weight (350 mg/plant) of soybean from combined application of co-inoculation of biofertilizers.

In addition, this result was in accord with Anteneh (2014) who conducted a field experiment that involved inoculation of two varieties of soybean with different strains of Rhizobium that increased nodule dry weight from 0.35 -0.46 g per plant.

Application of vermicompost also influenced significantly ($P < 0.001$) nodule dry weight per plant. A significantly higher number of nodule dry weight per plant (0.1665g/plant) was recorded with vermicompost as compared to without vermicompost (0.1050g/plant). (Table 10) This can be attributed to vermicompost's richness in organic matter and nutrients, including nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, which enhance soil fertility and promote common bean plant growth and nodule formation.

Vermicompost improves the activity of nitrogen-fixing bacteria like Rhizobium and contributing to higher nodule dry weights. Additionally, vermicompost enhances soil structure, porosity, and water retention capacity, creating conducive environment for root development and nodulation, which in turn leads to greater nodule formation and higher nodule dry weights. This result was similar to the finding of Woldesenbet (2021) Significantly higher number of nodule dry weight per plant of Faba bean (0.22 mg/plant) was recorded with vermicompost as compared to without vermicompost (0.1733 mg/plant).

Table 10: The main effect of Vermicompost and Rhizobium on nodule dry weight

Treatments	Nodule Dry Weight(g)
<i>Rhizobium</i>	
Inoculated	0.1504 ^a
Un-inoculated	0.1298 ^b
P-value	**
LSD^{0.05}	0.0133
VC(t/ha)	
0	0.1050 ^c
4	0.1665 ^a
8	0.148 ^b
P-value	**
LSD^{0.05}	0.0163
CV (%)	13.83

Interaction means within a columns followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different at $P > 0.05$; Ns = non-significant; *** = significant at $P \leq 0.001$, ** significant at $P \leq 0.01$; CV= Coefficient of variation, VC= Vermicompost rates.

4.4.3. The Effective Number of Nodules

The analysis of variance showed that the main effects of vermicompost, *Rhizobium*, and varieties were significantly ($P < 0.001$) influenced effective number of nodules per plant. Similarly, the two-factor interaction of vermicompost x *Rhizobium*, and vermicompost x variety had significant ($P < 0.001$) effects on these parameters. On the other hand, *Rhizobium* x variety had no significant effects on the effective number of nodules.

However, the three-factor interaction of vermicompost, *Rhizobium*, and variety had significant effects on the effective number of nodules per plant. (Appendix Table 5)

The highest number of effective nodules per plant resulted from the three-factor interaction (8 t/ha vermicompost rate and Hawassa Dume common bean variety inoculated with *Rhizobium* HP-429 strain) was 34.93, while the lowest (10.8) was recorded in the control treatment (0 t /ha VC rate and non-inoculated of SER- 125 common bean variety) (Table 11).

Increased in the number of effective nodules for interaction of VC and inoculation with variety regarding to Hawassa Dume might be attributed to its genetic characteristics such as extensive root system architecture. It also indicated that, this variety is producing more N₂ for the growth and development of the crop which is also directly determining factor to increase or decrease the yield of the crop. Similarly, Wendimu M., *et al.*, (2020) found that the highest effective nodule number of snap bean (155.58) was recorded from variety BC4.4 followed by variety Faraday (126.45) and variety Plati (122.29) probably be due to the genotype difference and *Rhizobium* strains found in nodule.

Fenta *et al.*, (2014) suggested that the distribution of roots, particularly those penetrating deeper into the soil, plays a crucial role in determining the ability of plants to capture key resources such as water and mobilize nutrients to maintain the water supply to the nodules which is an important trait that would facilitate higher rates of symbiotic nitrogen fixation (SNF).

The nutrients and organic matter provided by vermicompost contribute to improved soil health and nutrient availability, promoting vigorous root growth in common bean plants. Healthy root systems are conducive to nodulation, as they provide a suitable habitat for rhizobium colonization. Inoculation with effective rhizobium strains increases the population of nitrogen-fixing bacteria in the soil, leading to enhanced nodulation in common bean plants (Oyege, I., & Balaji Bhaskar, M. S. 2023).

Plants most susceptible to infection and capable of producing effective nodules should have a greater potential to fix more atmospheric nitrogen. This result is also supported by Gedamu, *et al.*, (2021) reported that inoculation of faba bean with rhizobium strain caused a noticeable increase in effective nodules per plant over un-inoculated treatment. Likewise, Bayou, *et al.*, (2021) reported that inoculation of NSFBR-15 to variety Dosha and TAL-1035 to variety Gora produced the highest number of effective nodules. Similarly, Abubakar, *et al.*, (2014) reported that inoculation of exotic and native *Bradyrhizobium* isolates produced effective nodules whereas the un-inoculated soybean failed to produce nodules. Awlachev, *et al.*, (2018) Also found that faba bean inoculation with the Degaga variety significantly increased effective nodule over control

Table 11:- Interaction effect of VC, Rhizobium and variety on effective number of nodules

		Effective Number of Nodules	
		<i>Rhizobium</i>	
VC(t/ha)	Varieties	Inoculated	Un-inoculated
0	Hawassa Dume	25.26 ^{dc}	21.86 ^e
	SER-125	26.60 ^d	10.80 ^f
4	Hawassa Dume	33.86 ^a	30.46 ^{abc}
	SER-125	32.00 ^{ab}	27.53 ^{cd}
8	Hawassa Dume	31.60 ^{ab}	28.40 ^{bcd}
	SER-125	30.93 ^{abc}	31.46 ^{ab}
P-value		**	
LSD^{0.05}		3.83	
CV (%)		8.24	

Effect means within a columns followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different at $P > 0.05$; NS = non-significant; *** = significant at $P \leq 0.001$, ** significant at $P \leq 0.01$; CV= Coefficient of variation, VC= Vermicompost rates.

4.5. Effects of Rhizobium, Vermicompost on Nitrogen Fixation of Common bean Varieties

The Fixed nitrogen, and %Ndfa were significantly influenced by the main effect of vermicompost, and variety, the two-way (vermicompost and *Rhizobium*), and three-way interaction (vermicompost x *Rhizobium* x variety).where as the main effect of *Rhizobium*, and the two way interaction of vermicompost and variety, and *Rhizobium* and variety had a non-significant effect on the nitrogen fixation and %Ndfa of the crop. Additionally, N-fixed and % Ndfa of common bean significantly increased with vermicompost and *Rhizobium* application (4, 8 t/ha VC, *Rhizobium* inoculated application on Hawassa Dume variety), whereas, the minimum result was obtained from application of 0 t/ha VC and *Rhizobium* on variety SER-125. (Table 12)

This might be due to vermicompost stimulates the biological state of the soil by stimulating the growth and effectiveness of microorganisms and their positive effects on plant growth by fixation of some elements such as atmospheric nitrogen or by dissolving and release some of the precipitated or fixed elements such as phosphorus and potassium.

Presences of *Rhizobium* with vermicompost, it attaches to the roots of the leguminous plant and produces nodules, these nodules fix atmospheric nitrogen and convert it into ammonia that can be used by the plant for its growth and development, as it interact with other microorganisms by improving plant growth by producing stimulants, growth regulators and enzymes and improving the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the yield as an increase in the percentage of protein in common bean seeds. These results were consistent with (Alkobaisy, J. *et al.*, 2021).

The addition of *Rhizobium* had significant effects on nitrogen fixation of beans. Similarly, there were significant differences in performance between the beans grown under the added vermicompost fertilizer or seed inoculation with *Rhizobium*.

The quantity of nitrogen fixed was notably influenced by seed inoculation, leading to a noticeable increase and a significant disparity between the inoculated group and the control. A crucial criterion for *Rhizobium* to be considered an effective bio-fertilizer is its exceptional nitrogen-fixing capacity and its ability to establish a symbiotic relationship with host plants (O'Hara *et al.*, 2002). This finding aligns with the results of Clayton *et al.*, (2004), who reported that nitrogen fixation was highest at 76.2% with rhizobia inoculation and lowest at 59% in the control field pea plants. Similar study was conducted by Asrat (2022) the highest Ndfa (74.4%) was recorded in plants inoculated with strain 1018 followed by plants inoculated with isolate FBR 15, whereas non inoculants resulted in the lowest Ndfa (64.8%).

The interaction of vermicompost and rhizobium with Hawassa Dume fixed more N and %Ndfa than SER-125. it might be because of it had a high nodule number, nodule dry weight, and effective nodule number. It had good nitrogen fixation capacities in all treatments. SER-125 had low nitrogen-fixing capacity and %Ndfa. This might be because N is redistributed mainly from the leaf and stem, respectively, to meet their seed N requirements and support high seed yield. This result confirms the important role of N redistribution in common beans from stems, leaves, and pod walls regardless of the nitrogen fixation ability of a genotype.

Vermicompost and Rhizobium can support common bean plants by providing additional nitrogen and creating favorable conditions for nitrogen fixation and nutrient uptake. This, combined with the plant's ability to redistribute nitrogen internally, contributes to higher seed yields and overall productivity in common bean cultivation.

Table 12: Interaction effect of VC, Rhizobium and variety on effective number of nodules, N-fixed and % Ndfa

		N-fixed(kg/ha)		%Ndfa	
Treatments		<i>Rhizobium</i>		<i>Rhizobium</i>	
VC(t/ha)	Varietes	Inoculated	Un-inoculated	Inoculated	Un-inoculated
0	Hawassa Dume	27.08 ^{cd}	29.34 ^c	28.4 ^{cd}	30 ^c
	SER-125	22.80 ^e	24.52 ^{de}	25 ^e	26.4 ^{de}
4	Hawassa Dume	47.74 ^a	46.12 ^a	41.2 ^a	40.3 ^a
	SER-125	38.40 ^b	45.35 ^a	36 ^b	39.9 ^a
8	Hawassa Dume	47 ^a	44.86 ^a	40.8 ^a	39.7 ^a
	SER-125	47.1 ^a	40.5 ^b	40.8 ^a	37.2 ^b
P-value		**		**	
LSD^{0.05}		3.387		2.161	
CV (%)		5.20		3.59	

Means within a columns followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different at $P > 0.05$; NS = non-significant; *** = significant at $P \leq 0.001$, ** significant at $P \leq 0.01$; CV= Coefficient of variation, VC= Vermicompost rates.

4.6. Effect of Rhizobium Inoculation, Vermicompost Application and Varieties on Yield and Yield Components of Common bean

4.6.1. Number of Pods per Plant (number)

The analysis of variance showed that the main effects of vermicompost and *Rhizobium* significant ($P < 0.001$) influence on the number of pods per plant. However, the main effects of variety did not have significant effects on the number of pods per plant. Similarly, two-factor interaction of vermicompost and variety, *Rhizobium* and variety did not influence the number of pods produced per plant. Nevertheless, the interaction of vermicompost and *Rhizobium* had a significant ($P < 0.001$) influence on the number of pods per plant. Three-factor interaction of vermicompost, *Rhizobium* and variety significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced the number of pods produced per plant. (Table 13)

The lowest number of pods per plant (9.41) was recorded from the control treatment (0 t/ha vermicompost + un-inoculated and SER 125 common bean variety). whereas the highest number of pods per plant (27.00) was recorded at the rate of 8 vermicompost t/ha inoculated with rhizobia strains and Hawassa Dume variety. (Table 13)

The positive effects of the inoculants might be due to the better amount of nitrogen rendered through nitrogen fixation which promoted vegetative growth and plant height and thus improved the number of pods per plant. This could again be attributed to the availability of vermicompost that would have increased the intensity of photosynthesis, nitrogen fixation, root development, flowering, seed formation, and fruiting.

A positive effect of seed inoculation on the number of pods was also reported by Tahir *et al.*,(2009). The authors reported that Rhizobium inoculated alone boosted the number of pods per plant by 85% over un-inoculated treatment.

Generally, the integrated use of organic, and bio-fertilizer influences the number of pods per plant. Increasing the rates of vermicompost increased the number of pods produced per plant across the rates of vermicompost, and Rhizobium inoculated with the HP-429 strain. This shows the synergistic effect of the fertilizers, mineralization of organic manures, and bio-fertilizer throughout the growing period did not put the plants under nutrient stress at any stage resulting in an enhanced number of pods per plant. Singh and Chauhan (2009) also reported that applying vermicompost and farmyard manures alone as well as in combination led to significant increases in growth and number of pods per plant.

Table 13: Interaction effect of vermicompost, *Rhizobium* and varieties on the number of pods per plant and number of seeds per pod

Treatments		Pods per Plant		Seeds per Pod	
VC t/ha	Varieties	<i>Rhizobium</i>			
		Inoculated	Un-inoculated	Inoculated	Un-inoculated
0	Hawassa Dume	19.00 ^{bc}	16.33 ^c	4.76 ^{cde}	4.36 ^c
	SER-125	20.26 ^{bc}	9.42 ^d	4.60 ^{de}	3.53 ^f
4	Hawassa Dume	20.13 ^{bc}	20.73 ^{bc}	5.43 ^b	4.90 ^{cd}
	SER-125	21.26 ^b	21.40 ^b	5.13 ^{bc}	4.90 ^{cd}
8	Hawassa Dume	27.00 ^a	21.93 ^b	6.00 ^a	5.03 ^{bcd}
	SER-125	22.33 ^b	21.93 ^b	5.26 ^{bc}	5.03 ^{bcd}
P-value		**		**	
LSD^{0.05}		4.5462		0.2088	
CV (%)		13.39		6.14	

Interaction means within a columns followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different from each other at $P > 0.05$; Ns = non-significant; *** = significant at $P \leq 0.001$, ** significant at $P \leq 0.01$; CV= Coefficient of variation, VC= Vermicompost rates.

4.6.2. Number of Seeds per Pod (number)

The main effects of vermicompost, *Rhizobium*, and variety significant ($P < 0.001$) influenced the number of seeds per pod. The two-factor interaction of vermicompost and *Rhizobium*, vermicompost and variety, and *Rhizobium* x variety did not significantly influence the number of seeds per pod produced by the plant.

Nevertheless, the three-factor interaction of vermicompost, *Rhizobium* and variety significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected the number of seeds per pod produced by the plant (Appendix Table).

Seed number increment with inoculation and vermicompost application might be due to the contribution of inoculation and organic fertilizer to each other to reach the state of optimal nutritional balance suitable for the growth and development of the plant (Kebede G, *et al.*, 2023). The increase of seed per pod on Hawassa Dume variety might be because of the highest number of branches per plant and the number of pods per plant of the variety.

In line with, (Anteneh and Abere 2017) found that the integrated use of high-quality vermicompost and *Rhizobium* inoculation significantly increased the number of seeds per pod of faba bean over the control treatment. (Azarpour *et al.*, 2012) Also reported that the number of seeds per plant of faba bean was recorded from seed inoculation with nitroxin combined with 10 ton/ha vermicompost treatments while the lowest number of seeds was recorded from the control treatment. Similarly, (Kumar *et al.*, 2018) reported that the use of phosphate-solubilizing bacteria and one strain of *Rhizobium* bacteria in combination with vermicomposting in faba bean plants increased the number of seeds per pod over-control plot.

4.6.3. Thousand Seed Weights (g)

Thousand seed weight is an important yield trait often associated positively with seed yield (Fageria *et al.*, 2009). Analysis of variance revealed that the main effects of vermicompost, *Rhizobium*, and variety significantly ($P < 0.001$), ($P < 0.05$) influenced thousand seed weights of common bean. However, the two-factor interactions and three-factor interaction had no significant effects on thousand seed weights.

Inoculated treatments achieved significant increases in thousand seed weight (240.30g) compared to un-inoculated treatments (230.74g), (Table 14) which could be due to the symbiotic relationship between *Rhizobium* and common bean plants, which results in the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen in to the roots and translocation of amino acids to the shoots, thus leading to increased seed size and content of grain protein. Inoculants play an important role in improving growth and assimilating accumulations thereby increasing the reproductive performance of the plants, which leads to large grain production (Tarekegn, 2011).

In line with this result, Aemiro (2020) reported that Inoculated treatments achieved significant increases in hundred seed weight (71.6 g) compared to un-inoculated treatments (68.5g). Bezabih (2018) reported that *rhizobium* inoculation increased the 100 gain weight of faba bean by 11.44%, compared to uninoculated treatment.

Similarly, Solomon *et al.* (2012) also reported that *BradyRhizobium japonicum* inoculation highly increased 100 grain weight of soybean. The other study on lentils also indicated that 100-grain weight was significantly higher in inoculated treatments in the pot experiment than in the un-inoculated (control) treatment (Wondwosen *et al.*, 2016). Lamptey *et al.* (2014) also reported the positive effects of *rhizobium* inoculation on yield of various leguminous crops.

The highest 1000 grain weight (244.36 g/plot) was recorded at vermicompost rate of 4t/ha statistically similar to 8 t/ha (243.17 g /plot)while the lowest 1000 gain weight (219.03 g/plot) was recorded which plot without vermicompost application (control treatment) (Table 14). The variation in grain weight might be because vermicompost possessed higher and more soluble forms of major nutrients such as N, P, K, Ca, S, and Mg (Reddy, 2004).

Thousand-grain weights were directly influenced by the photosynthetic material after it is pollinated, the plant material of current photosynthesis or remobilization can be stored in the stems, leaves, or pods provided (Ahmadi and Bahrani .2009). Akbari *et al.*, (2009) also reported that an increased grain weight during the grain-filling period had been accounted for and can show the effect of photosynthetic bacteria, enhancing plant growth by increasing the amount of material stored in the grain-filling period. The use of vermicomposting, biological nitrogen, and root, optimal absorption of water and nutrients, and production of some vitamins increases followed by qualitative and quantitative growth of the plant and thereby strengthening weight gain would be determined for thousand seeds weight (Kumar *et al.*, 2007).

This study shows that the highest 1000 seed weight (240.30 g/plot) was recorded at Hawassa Dume variety while the lowest 1000 seed weight (230.97g/ plot) was recorded at which SER 125 common bean variety. (Table 14) Amanullah and Asim (2011) reported that hundred seed weight varied significantly among haricot bean varieties from 19.5 to 61.5g.

In line with Aseffa *et al.*, 2017, Pointed out that different seed sizes might influence seed weight, which is a result of different origins of varieties, and also management influenced seed weight. This might be attributed to the result of nutrient availability. On the other hand, the role of genetic potential which described in two important ways; those were the ability of varieties to withstand nutrient deficiency stress, and natural behavior that produces large seed sizes.

Table 14:- The main effect of vermicompost Rhizobium and variety on 1000 seed weight, above ground biomass and harvesting index.

Treatments	1000 Seed Weight(g)	AGB(kg/ha)	Harvesting Index
Rhizobium			
Inoculated	240.30 ^a	7433.01 ^a	0.4359
Un-inoculated	230.74 ^b	6699.08 ^b	0.4387
P –value	**	**	NS
LSD^{0.05}	8.2625	539.47	
Vermicompost (t/ha)			
0	219.03 ^b	5453.35 ^b	0.4404
4	243.17 ^a	7866.94 ^a	0.4232
8	244.36 ^a	7877.85 ^a	0.4482
P –value	*	**	NS
LSD0.05	10.119	660.72	
Varieties			
Hawassa Dume	240.30 ^a	7121.81	0.4605 ^a
SER-125	230.74 ^b	7010.22	0.4141 ^b
P-value	*	NS	*
LSD^{0.05}	8.2625		0.0424
CV (%)	5.09	11.09	14.09

Mean within the same columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different at a 5% level of significance; NS= not significantly; ** = significant at $P \leq 0.01$; *** = significant at $P \leq 0.001$; CV= Coefficient of variation, VC= vermicompost

4.6.4. Above-Ground Biomass Yield (kg/ha)

The analysis of variance showed that the main effects of vermicompost and *Rhizobium* were significant ($P < 0.001$), ($P < 0.05$) influenced above-ground biomass yield respectively, whereas varieties of common bean had no significant effect in these parameters. The two-factor interaction of vermicompost and *Rhizobium*, vermicompost and variety and *Rhizobium* and variety had no significant effect on the above-ground biomass of the yield. Similarly, the three-factor interaction of vermicompost, *Rhizobium* and variety had no significant affected the above-ground biomass of common beans.

Increasing biomass was observed in response to the application of a higher vermicompost rate of 8 t/ha which was 7877.85 kg/ha but it is statistically similar to the rate of 4 t/ ha vermicompost (7866.94). However, the minimum biomass was measured at the application of 0 t/ha VC (5453.35 kg/ha). This could be because vermicompost has better soil properties that encourage root growth, which could lead to higher growth of above-ground plant parts.

Increases in the growth components of common beans, such as leaves, stems, and grain, as well as water retention as a consequence of the high specific area properties of vermicompost fed to the soil, lead to an increase in the crop's above-ground biomass. Additionally, applying vermicompost to the crop during the growth phase may result in favorable conditions for yield-determining components and, consequently, biological yield. Vermicompost contains sufficient quantities of vital plant nutrients.

In line with this result Islam. M. et al (2016) also stated that total biomass of the three legumes, namely bush bean, winged bean, and yard long bean were significantly increased with application of (20%) vermicompost than control treatments.

The highest above-ground dry biomass (7433.01 kg/ha) was recorded from the *Rhizobium* inoculation while the lowest above-ground dry biomass (6699.08 kg/ha) was recorded without *Rhizobium* inoculation. (Table 14) In agreement with this result Gedamu. *et al.*, (2021) reported that inoculation of faba bean with EAL-1018 strain gave maximum (10.277 ton/ha) biomass yield than EAL-1035 (9.361 ton/ha) and EAL-17 (8.329 ton/ha) while the lowest biomass yield was obtained from the control treatment (7.327 ton/ha).

The significantly higher above-ground dry biomass induced by *Rhizobium* inoculation might be due to the presence of high N derived from biological nitrogen fixation leading to high biomass formation. Also, it might be due to the increasing uptake of nutrients due to *Rhizobium* inoculation. In agreement with this result, Biswas *et al.*, (2000) reported that *rhizobia* inoculants may also induce an increased number of root hairs and lateral roots thereby favoring nutrient uptake by exploration of a greater soil volume. Similarly, Asad *et al.*, (2004) reported that inoculation of mung bean with a selected strain of *Rhizobium* resulted in a significant increment of the dry matter production over un-inoculated one. As well as Malik *et al.*, (2006) also reported that nitrogen fixation by *Rhizobium* hastened the vegetative growth; it improved the yield components of soybean which is the possible reason for a substantial increase in above-ground dry biomass.

4.6.5. Harvest Index

The Harvest index was not affected due to the main effects of vermicompost, *Rhizobium*, and the interaction terms of vermicompost and *Rhizobium*, vermicompost and variety, *Rhizobium* and variety, (Appendix 7) whereas varieties of common bean had significant effect on this parameter.

In this experiment, the highest harvest index was recorded from Hawassa Dume variety (0.4605) treatment, while the lowest 0.4141 harvest index was obtained from SER-125 common bean variety. (Table 14) The highest mean harvest index also implies higher partitioning of the dry matter into seed. This variation could be due to different growth and development of the varieties. Positive variation in HI values among treatments might be attributed to variability in varieties in response to applied rates of fertilization (Amare, *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, it was indicated that variation in HI values might be attributed to inherent differences in common bean varieties.

4.6.6. Grain Yield (kg/ha)

Analysis of variance showed that the main effect of (*Rhizobium*, vermicompost, and variety) and the two-way interaction effects of vermicompost with variety showed a significant effect on grain yield of common bean, while the three-way interaction effects of (*Rhizobium* inoculation, vermicompost application, and variety), and the others interaction effect was non-significant on this parameter.

In this study, the two-way interaction effects of vermicompost with variety showed a significant effect on the grain yield of common bean so the maximum yield value was obtained from the application of 8 t/ha of VC and Hawassa Dume common bean variety (3641.65 kg/ha), while it is statistically similar with 4 t/ha of VC+ Hawassa Dume common bean variety (3327.35 kg/ha), 8 t/ha of VC + SER-125 common bean variety(3355.15 kg/ha), and 4 t/ha of VC and SER-125 common bean variety (3292.28 kg/ha). Numerically, the highest mean grain yield was obtained from the application of 8 t/ha of VC on Hawassa Dume common bean variety and the lowest was recorded at the control treatment, which was 0 t/ha vermicompost and SER-125 common bean variety (2035.37 kg/ha). (Table 15)

The positive effects of vermicompost on common bean productivity could be due to vermicompost not only increasing the microbial activity in the supply of phosphorus and nitrogen fixation but also increasing mineralization of soil organic matter so that more crop nutrient needs were met. The results of the present study conform to the work of (Ebrahim, 2012). Vermicompost application significantly increases the grain yields of legumes this might be due to the activity of humic acids which is found in vermicompost (Ravimycin, 2016). Accordingly Basdemir, F., *et al.*, (2022) reported that the highest seed yield of common bean (2364 kg ha⁻¹) was fertilized with 5 t ha⁻¹ cow manure + 100% recommended dose of vermicompost and the lowest yield (1137 kg ha⁻¹) was obtained from control.

This higher yield from the application of vermicompost, on Hawassa Dume common bean variety may be attributable to the availability of macro and micro-nutrients, and occurrence of different beneficial microorganisms, presence of growth-promoting substances. Similarly Singh and Chauhan (2009), reported that applied vermicompost, and farmyard manure, alone as well as in combination to study their effect on yield of common beans.

The results of this study showed increased grain yields in response to the increasing rate of vermicompost application. The increase in grain yield might be attributed to overall improvement in growth attributes such as above ground dry biomass yield and the number of primary branches thereby increasing yield-attributing traits such as the number of pods per plant, and thousand seed weight. Several authors also reported an association of an increase in these yield-attributing traits with an increase in grain yield (Ali *et al.*, 2002; Sofi *et al.*, 2011).

Common bean varieties reacted differently to variable rates of vermicompost. Hawassa Dume, grain yield increased with increasing vermicompost rates from 0 to 8 t/ha and then peaked at a rate of 8 t/ha and 4 t/ha. Thus, grain yield varied from 2746.33 to 3641 kg/ha with respective vermicompost rates.

This might be due to Hawassa Dume variety had ability to produce more pods/plant and higher seed number/pod, which increased its grain yield as a crop. The higher grain yield could also be attributed to the better plant growth of Hawassa Dume and perhaps, its increased nodulation or symbiotic performance.

Difference in seed yield due to variety is by the genetic performance that each variety has to adapt to different environmental conditions. These results were supported by Lunze, L.*et al.*, (2012) who demonstrated that the seed yield of common beans varied significantly between varieties during different cropping seasons in different agro-ecological zones of North and Sud-Kivu. Genetic performance is one of the indicators of agricultural production, since each variety has its own capacity to produce a potential yield in different agro ecological areas Casinga, *et al.*,(2015).

Table 15: Interaction effects of vermicompost, and varieties on grain yield

Grain Yield(kg/ha)		
	Varieties	
VC (t/ha)	Hawassa Dume	SER-125
0	2746.33 ^b	2035.37 ^c
4	3327.35 ^a	3292.28 ^a
8	3641.65 ^a	3355.15 ^a
P-value	*	
LSD^{0.05}	411.5	
CV (%)	11.38	

Means within a columns followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different from each other at $P > 0.05$; ns = non-significant; *** = significant at $P \leq 0.001$, ** significant at $P \leq 0.01$; CV= Coefficient of variation, VC= Vermicompost rates.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1. Conclusions

Ensuring a well-balanced supply of *Rhizobium* inoculation, vermicompost to the common bean crop resulted in higher grain yield through improving nodule activities and nitrogen fixation. In conclusion, the application of Vermicompost and Rhizobium had varying effects on soil properties in the study.

These findings indicate that the application of Vermicompost had positive effects on soil fertility, as evidenced by the increased availability of phosphorus and improved nutrient content. Additionally, Vermicompost alone contributed to enhanced soil water retention capabilities, potentially benefiting plant growth and development.

It is important to consider these results when making decisions regarding soil management practices, as the application of Vermicompost can potentially improve soil fertility and moisture retention.

This experiment revealed that the choice of common bean varieties had a significant influence on specific growth and yield parameters, namely days to 50% flowering, effective number of nodules, nitrogen fixation (N-fixed), percentage of nitrogen derived from the atmosphere (%Ndfa), number of seeds per pod, number of primary branches, thousand seed weight, and grain yield.

These findings suggest that different varieties of common bean can exhibit variations in their reproductive and nitrogen-fixing capabilities, as well as seed development and overall yield.

On the other hand, certain parameters such as number of nodules, nodule dry weight, plant height, above ground biomass, number of pods per plant, and harvest index were not significantly affected by the choice of common bean varieties. This indicates that these particular characteristics may be less influenced by genetic differences among the tested varieties. Overall, the study highlights the importance of selecting appropriate common bean varieties to maximize specific traits and optimize yield potential in agricultural production systems.

The study demonstrated that vermicompost, Rhizobium inoculation, and variety selection have a significant influence on various growth and yield parameters of common bean. The interaction between these factors further amplified their effects on different aspects of plant performance.

Vermicompost and Rhizobium inoculation applied together at a rate of 8 t/ha, showed the most promising results in terms of enhancing common bean yield. This integrated approach not only improved soil fertility but also reduced the reliance on costly inorganic fertilizers, offering a sustainable and effective strategy for Ethiopian farmers to increase their common bean production. Furthermore, the findings suggest that this approach can contribute to improved food security and economic prosperity by providing higher yields and benefiting subsequent crops.

5.2. Recommendations

Based on the study results obtained on nodulation, yield, and yield component the following recommendations could be forwarded.

- ✓ Farmers in the study areas could sustainably enhance the yield of common bean by applying 8 t vermicompost ha⁻¹ in combination with *Rhizobium* inoculated HP-429 strain.
- ✓ Among the varieties Hawassa Dume variety could be recommended for the study area since it had better performances compared to SER-125.

However, effect of vermicompost refers to the long-term impact it has on soil fertility and plant growth even after the initial application. Because of this and other factors experiment has to be repeated for areas under similar agro-ecological condition to confirm the validity of the present findings since the research is done in one location for a single season.

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Appendix 1: Rating for soil pH (H₂O), bulk density, OM and TN

pH^a	Rating	Bulk	Rating	OM%^c	TN%^c	Rating
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Density(gm/cm ³) ^b						
<4.5	Very strong acid	<1.0	Very low	<0.86	<0.05	Very low
4.5-5.2	Strong acid	1.0-1.3	Low	0.86-2.59	0.05-1.25	low
5.3-5.9	Moderately acid	1.3-1.6	Moderate	2.59-5.17	0.12-0.25	Medium
6.0-6.6	Slightly acid	1.6-1.9	High	>5.17	>0.25	High
6.7-7.3	Neutral	>1.9	Very high			
7.4-8.4	Moderately alkaline					
>8.0	Strongly alkaline					

Source: Tekaligne Mamo (1991)a, Hunt and Gilkes (1992)b and Tekalign Mamo (1999)c.

Appendix 3: Rating for available phosphors and cation exchange capacity

P(mg/kg) ^a	Rating	CEC ^b	Rating
<0.5	Very low	<6	Very low
5-9	Low	6.0-12.0	Low
10-17	Moderate	12.0-15.0	Medium
18-25	High	25.0-24.0	High
>25	Very high	>40	Very high

Source: Olsen *et al.* (1954) a and Hazelton and Murphy (2007)b

Appendix 5: Mean square values of days to flower initiation, plant height, total number of nodules per plant, and effective nodules, as influenced by VC, R, VAR, and their interaction

effects* Significant at $p \leq 0.05$; ** significant at $p \leq 0.01$; *** significant at $p \leq 0.001$; ns= non-significant at $p > 0.05$.

SV	DF	MS					
		Ph	PP	F	ENN	NN	NDW
VC	2	1012.1353**	153.8265**	110.25**	372.8933**	136.303**	0.0120***
R	1	316.00**	83.2656 **	36.00**	221.017**	129.201**	0.0038**
VAR	1	36.8044 Ns	18.1334Ns	7.1111**	36.804**	4.134Ns	0.0008Ns
VC x R	2	70.5058*	38.2881**	0.7500**	53.604**	13.121Ns	0.0007Ns
VC x VAR	2	16.4669Ns	12.2859Ns	0.8611**	27.924**	44.367 Ns	0.00003Ns
Rx VAR	1	0.2844Ns	3.9667 Ns	0.4444**	23.6844*	39.690**	0.000007Ns
VC x R x VAR	2	0.4853Ns	31.3776**	3.6944**	51.4711**	7.203 Ns	0.0003Ns
Total	11						
CV (%)		5.15	13.39	0.63	8.24	7.21	13.86

Whereas= SV: source of variation, Df: degree of freedom, MS: mean square, Ph: plant height, PP: pod per plant, F: 50% of flowering date, NN: Number of nodule, ENN: Effective number of nodule, NDW: nodules dry weight, VC: vermicompost, R: Rhizobium, VAR: variety.

Appendix 6: Mean square values of Number of branches, Seed per pod, Above ground biomass and grain yield as influenced by VC, R and VAR their interaction effects ** Ns = not significant at $P \leq 0.05$ *, **: significantly at $P \leq 0.05$ and $P \leq 0.01$. Respectively.

SV	DF	MS			
		NB	SP	AGB	GY
VC	2	50.803**	3.3853**	23407383.29**	4213428.4**
R	1	5.6011**	2.9469 **	4847879.2*	812107.4**
VAR	1	8.4100**	1.0336**	112198.2 Ns	1066131.9**
VC X R	2	0.5144Ns	0.0936 Ns	258692.13 Ns	21276.58 Ns
VC X VAR	2	1.8633**	0.0936Ns	1708291.09Ns	350114.29*
R X VAR	1	0.0100Ns	0.0336Ns	708694.6Ns	207145Ns
VCXRVAR	2	0.4233Ns	0.3853*	192455.34 Ns	58792 Ns
Total	11				
CV (%)		8.25	6.12	11.29	10.60

Whereas= SV: source of variation, Df: degree of freedom, MS: mean square, NB: Number of branches, SP: Seeds per pod, AGB: Above ground biomass, GY: Grain yield, VC: vermicompost, R: rhizobium, VAR: variety.

Appendix 7: Mean square values of harvesting index, thousand seed weight, N-fixed and %Ndfa as influenced by VC, R and VAR their interaction effects ** Ns = not significant at $P \leq 0.05$ *, **: significantly at $P \leq 0.05$ and $P \leq 0.01$. Respectively

SV	DF	MS			
		HI	TSW	N-fixed	%Ndfa
VC	2	0.0019 Ns	2451.68**	1398.3193**	577.3739**
Rhizobium	1	0.00006Ns	821.20*	0.0831Ns	0.5351 Ns
Variety	1	0.0193 *	744.07*	138.1016**	55.7662**
VCXR	2	0.00042 Ns	337.62 Ns	45.2875**	15.2735**
VCXVAR	2	0.0086 Ns	24.4739Ns	7.1917Ns	4.166208**
RXVAR	1	0.000009Ns	67.6232 Ns	3.1388Ns	1.07575Ns
VCXRXVAR	2	0.0012 Ns	81.1020 Ns	33.4805**	10.3672**
Total	11				
CV (%)		14.09	4.71	5.15	3.56

Whereas= SV: source of variation, Df: degree of freedom, MS: mean square, HI: Harvesting index, TSW: Thousand seed weight, VC: vermicompost, R: rhizobium, VAR: variety.

Figure 2. Appendix figures, Field work

Figure 3. Appendix figures. Laboratory work

BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

The author was born on May 29, 1997, GC to her father Mr. Tolessa Sedi, and her mother Mrs. Gete Kumssa at Wenbera, Metekel Zone of Benishangul Gumz national regional state, Ethiopia. She attended her elementary and secondary school education at Wenbera Elementary and secondary school and Wenbera Preparatory School respectively. Then, she joined Haramaya University in September 2016 GC and graduated with a BSc degree in Natural Resource Management in July, 2018 GC.

After her graduation, she worked in Ethiopian Institute of Agriculture Research (EIAR) for three years. After serving for about three years, she joined the regular postgraduate program at Hawassa University College of Agriculture on October 2021 to pursue her study leading to MSc degree in the field of Soil Science.